

**TUNNELING TRANSPORT IN
TWO-DIMENSIONAL CONDUCTORS AND
DIRAC/WEYL SEMIMETALS**

ISMAIL CAN YESILYURT

B. Eng. (Hons.), Okan University

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Supervisors:

Associate Professor Mansoor Bin Abdul Jalil, Main Supervisor

Associate Professor Liang Gengchiao, Co-Supervisor

Dr Tan Seng Ghee, Co-Supervisor:

Examiners:

Associate Professor Yang Hyunsoo

Professor Feng Yuan Ping

Professor Shen Shun Qing, The University of Hong Kong

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SUMMARY

Different forms of crystal structures generally possess very different electrical, optical, and mechanical properties. During the last decade, researchers spent a considerable amount of effort in investigating Dirac semimetals with linear low energy dispersion constituted by hexagonal lattices such as graphene. Tunneling transport in such condensed matter materials constitutes the heart of novel electronic transport applications. The chiral structure of Dirac fermions allows tunneling transport between electron and hole states, which makes the Klein paradox possible in condensed matter systems. In the case of broken inversion or time reversal symmetry, an individual Dirac fermion can split into multiple Weyl fermions with different chiralities. Low crystal symmetry gives rise to a non-trivial, tilted anisotropic band structure. In this Thesis, we investigate several aspects of tunneling properties of Dirac and Weyl semimetals, which include spin and valley dependent transport as well as consequences of the tilted energy dispersion.

First, we focus on tunneling transport in two-dimensional conductors such as graphene and silicene and investigate their spin and valley dependent transport properties. A silicene-based, efficient dual spin-valley filter application is proposed, which exploits the out-of-plane displacement between sublattices that induces spin-dependent potential in the presence of magnetic insulators attached to the silicene layer, and uniaxial strain that induces valley dependent gauge potential. Besides, we propose an efficient ($\approx 100\%$) valley selective barrier structure based on graphene, where high polarization can be achieved in conjunction with high conductance regime. The

Summary

proposed scheme provides a solution to a common problem of previously presented methods, i.e., high valley polarization at the cost of low conductance.

In the second part of the Thesis, we performed an extensive study of the consequences of tilted energy dispersion in Weyl semimetals. We found that carriers encountering an electrical potential barrier experience anisotropic refractions at the barrier interface. The resultant effect is equivalent to that of a momentum dependent magnetic field as the coupling of tilted dispersion and electrical potential gradient effectively shifts the Fermi surface of the system at the barrier interface, which is analogous to the shift caused by transverse Lorentz displacement. Besides, we analytically derive the equivalent magnetic field as a function of the tilt velocity.

The predicted tilt-induced transverse momentum shift is valley dependent property when two Weyl fermions are tilted along different directions. We utilize this to design a novel valley filtering method. In the proposed method, the valley degeneracy is lifted by the electrical potential, where electrons belong to different valleys experience different direction refractions. Hence, the carrier trajectories become valley dependent property. A magnetic barrier configuration is used to break the angular symmetry of transmission, which results in valley dependent conductance.

We also show that the tilted energy dispersion can significantly affect the conductance modulation in Dirac and Weyl semimetals, a property which can be utilized to resolve a major problem of Dirac/Weyl semimetal-based transistor applications, i.e., the absence of backscattering. The proposed scheme enables us to obtain a large conductance gap as well as large transconductance in tilted Weyl semimetal systems in the presence of magnetic barriers.

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LIST OF SYMBOLS AND ABBREVIATIONS

DOS	density of states
FM	ferromagnet
NEGF	non-equilibrium Green's function
SOC	spin-orbit coupling
QW	quantum well
c	speed of light
m	mass
e	electron charge
V_0	Electrical potential
t	local hopping energy
k_B	Boltzmann constant
$T(\phi)$	Transmission probability as a function of incident angle (ϕ)
E_F	Fermi energy
\hbar	plank constant / 2π
A_S	strain gauge potential
k_F	Fermi wave-vector
l_B	magnetic length
B_0	magnetic field strength

List of Symbols and Abbreviations

j	current density
G_0	quantum conductance
μ	chemical potential
I	current
$M(E)$	number of modes
L	channel length
W	channel width

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background and motivation

Tunneling transmission of particles is a pure quantum mechanical effect which has no counterpart in classical physics [1, 2]. The phenomenon can be defined in such a manner that a particle with energy (E) encounters a barrier or well with potential (V), and finite transmission probability occurs even in the case of $E < V$. This behavior is associated with many fundamental phenomena, such as radioactive decay [3] where a nucleus emits an alpha particle that is confined by high potential before decay.

Quantum mechanical tunneling is also utilized in nanoelectronic transport applications based on semiconductors [4, 5]. In semiconductors, tunneling junctions can be designed by fabricating two conductor parts separated by a thin insulator or a heavily doped region. Such methods are used in various applications such as tunnel diode [6] and tunnel field effect transistor [2]. Besides, the application of heavy doping or gated potential barriers provide a platform for achieving highly confined electrons, i.e., so-called quantum-dot [7, 8], which constitutes a crucial part of solid state quantum computing.

Introduction

Tunneling properties in crystal structures are highly related to the electrical, physical, and magnetic features of the host conducting material. Therefore, tunneling transport in semimetallic materials has attracted great attention in recent years. What is notably different in such materials from the usual conductors and semiconductors is their chiral and topological features. Many novel electrical transport properties are associated with the unique band structure features of such materials which may pave the way for novel physics and applications. Hence, the focus of this Thesis lies on tunneling transport in Dirac/Weyl semimetals. A detailed overview of tunneling transport in two- and three-dimensional semimetals is provided in the following sections. In such materials, spin and valley degree of freedom also play a crucial role in tunneling transport, which is widely investigated in this Thesis.

1.1.1 Klein tunneling

In conventional tunneling transport, the transmission probability (T) exponentially decays with increasing potential (V). However, Klein paradox [9] states that an electron that encounters a potential barrier with height V_0 transmits with high probability if V_0 exceeds the rest energy of electron (mc^2). This effect can be explained by the propagating positron states in the barrier region whose energy matches with that of incident electrons. Therefore, the wave functions of incident electron and propagating positron states have some overlap, which leads to high transmission probability across the barrier. This phenomenon is called Klein paradox, which had been thought impossible to prove experimentally since the required potential barrier height must exceed mc^2 (≈ 0.5 MeV), i.e., not possible in current technology.

Recent developments in condensed matter physics have reawakened interest in the Klein paradox because materials such as graphene possess Dirac fermions with touching valance and conduction band without an energy gap. In such systems, Klein tunneling

occurs when the energy, momentum, and chirality are matched in the incident and barrier regions [10]. In the following sections, Klein tunneling in Dirac and Weyl semimetals including electron-optic and spin and valley dependent tunneling properties is widely investigated. Although Klein tunneling has been extensively studied in the context of graphene, it is not investigated in Weyl semimetals yet. Despite the low energy Weyl dispersion being basically the three-dimensional counterpart of graphene's energy dispersion, and possessing similar chiral structure, Weyl points are generally located at low symmetry points, which gives rise to an anisotropic energy dispersion unlike that of graphene. Therefore, we also aim to study the effect of anisotropic band structure on the Klein tunneling properties.

1.1.2 Spin and valley degree of freedom

Besides of electrical charge, particles may also carry spin degree of freedom which is utilized to develop so-called spintronic devices [11–13]. Quantum mechanical spin of particles is useful in several fields in electronics. Since spin constitutes one of the origins of magnetism in magnetic materials, data storage methods generally lie behind manipulating the spin of localized or conducting electrons [14]. Beside of localized spin and orbital angular momentum, spin current can be defined as a finite spin polarization of electrical current. It can be generated or injected into a material [12], giving rise to remarkable new features of spintronic systems. Spin current has offered a new approach for manipulation of the spin and orbital angular momentum, and hence the magnetization of the host material. Remarkably, spin current based magnetic switching has been realized in commercial data storage devices in recent years.

Data storage is not the only field that spin degree is useful; the spin current has also paved the way for novel transistor applications such as spin field effect transistors [15], and logic devices based on manipulation of spin chemical potential [16].

Valley isospin [17] is another feature of electrons, which can be useful in novel electronic devices. Electrical band structure of some condensed matter materials possesses inequivalent valleys, i.e., defined as energy minima (maxima) in the conduction (valence) band [17]. Thus, in such materials, electrons around different valleys exhibit different electrical and magnetic properties, and these valley-dependent properties can be utilized in a similar way as the real spin degree of freedom [17].

1.1.3 Manipulating spin and valley degree in tunneling applications

Real spin and valley isospin originate from different physics, and thus the generation and detection mechanisms are quite different.

Since spin angular momentum gives rise to magnetic moment, one can thus manipulate the spin degree with magnetic interactions, which constitutes the basis of spin current generation methods. For instance, spin current can be injected to any conductor using ferromagnetic heterojunctions [12]. This can be understood by the concept that ferromagnetic materials possess spin-dependent density of states for electrons, leading to spin dependent conductivities.

On the other hand, the methods that are used to generate valley polarization are generally based on electrical or mechanical properties. For instance, valley degeneracy can be lifted by applying strain on materials that possess particular hexagonal lattices or applying sublattice dependent potential via various methods [18–24].

A significant amount of effort has been spent to obtain spin and valley polarized conductance by designing spin and valley selective tunneling barriers. In the literature, there are many significant works investigating the spin and valley dependent tunneling in novel materials [24–27]. However, controlling spin and valley transport, and maintaining high polarization are still major issues to be addressed. In this Thesis, we will propose

different device structures and utilize exotic features of emerging condensed matter materials to resolve existing problems and improve the efficiency of previous proposals. Specifically, spin, valley, and dual spin-valley dependent tunneling conductance will be investigated in various condensed matter materials as described in the next Section.

1.1.4 Emerging condensed matter materials

Material science is the heart of novel electronic applications as the modulation and change of electrical conductivity due to applied fields, temperature, or impurity doping are generally related to the material properties. Semiconductor technology has paved the way for many novel applications and constitutes the basis of the traditional diode and transistor [4, 5, 28–30]. The major problem of the semiconductor technology is that the number of transistors in an integrated circuit doubles every two years in order to attain ever higher processing speed (i.e., known as Moore's law). Although recent advances have enabled the size of transistors to get smaller day by day, this brings about a different set of problems such as heat dissipation. Therefore, in order to overcome these problems the search for novel nano-electronic materials that possess high conductivity with favorable mechanical, optical, and magnetic properties has been a major objective for scientists in recent years.

Unlike semiconductors, numerous materials such as graphene, silicene, and topological insulators possess massless Dirac particles that do not obey the usual Schrödinger Hamiltonian [31, 32]. This class of materials are called "Dirac materials". The massless behavior of electrons leads to very high conductivity that is unattainable in semiconductors. The high mobility in such materials enables highly ballistic conductance, which allows the realization and observation of various condensed matter phenomena that require long mean free path.

Introduction

Dirac materials generally exhibit semimetallic electrical band structure where the conductance and valence band touch each other without any overlap [31]. Furthermore, the chiral nature of Dirac fermions and gapless band structure has enabled the realization of interesting tunneling applications such as Klein tunneling [10]. In the following sections, tunneling transport is investigated in several Dirac semimetals such as graphene and silicene.

In two-dimensional Dirac semimetals, fermions are generally located at high symmetry points in momentum space [31]. Breaking the time reversal symmetry or inversion symmetry in a Dirac semimetal separates a Dirac node (four band crossing) into two Weyl nodes (two band crossing) separated in momentum space, which allows tilted band structure to occur [33–37]. In this Thesis, it is shown that the effect of tilted energy dispersion leads unique transport properties in Weyl semimetals.

1.2 Objectives

In this Thesis, we aim to investigate tunneling transport in Dirac and Weyl semimetals, including the design of spin and valley selective electro-magnetic barriers. The previously proposed methods have some fundamental drawbacks including low conductance at high polarization regime and poor conductance modulation ability due to the absence of backscattering. We aim to resolve these problems by optimizing the existing models and proposing novel approaches based on different device structures or different materials having distinct transport properties. The unique electrical band structures of materials such as Weyl semimetals leads to exotic and intriguing transport properties. Especially, in such materials with tilted energy dispersion, the tunneling properties have been less studied. We would show that this unique property allows us to control electrical charge and valley current efficiently. Therefore, one of the objectives of this Thesis is to investigate the consequences of tilted energy dispersion in terms of several

aspects including angular dependence of tunneling probability and valley dependent refractions at the electrical barrier interfaces. The specific objectives in order to reach above targets are as follows:

- Study spin and valley dependent transport mechanisms in graphene and silicene, and how the polarization and conductance can be optimized.
- Investigate Klein tunneling transport in Weyl semimetals including the effect of tilted energy dispersion.
- Design a conductance modulation approach based on Weyl semimetals, in order to provide a solution of a major conductance modulation problem, i.e., the absence of backscattering.
- Design electrically tunable valley filter in Weyl semimetals which ensures high controllability and robustness.

1.3 Organization of Thesis

The physics of the findings and proposed applications in this Thesis share a common phenomenon, i.e., tunneling transport. Therefore we first provide a theoretical background of tunneling transport in the targeted materials. The material-specific calculations and modifications are provided in each chapter. The works presented in the rest of the chapters are focused on transport properties of unique emerging materials and/or current unresolved issues of tunneling applications and devices, which are mentioned above. Different materials and device structures are studied in terms of electrical transport, and each of the works is focused on a particular goal as stated below. The unifying theme of our works is the study of charge, spin, and valley transport in emerging condensed matter systems.

Introduction

In Chapter 2, technical background on tunneling transport in Dirac materials is presented in detail. We first analyze the electrical band structure of graphene and silicene, which is the key element for tunneling transmission calculations frequently used in the subsequent parts. Several possible external effects such as strain and induced exchange interaction are introduced. Angular dependence of tunneling transmission in graphene and silicene is investigated in single and double potential barrier structures. We then provide background information about magnetic barriers, which will be used in the proposed applications.

In Chapter 3, we present novel designs of spin and valley dependent tunneling barriers in two separate main sections. In the first section, we show that a pure valley polarization can be achieved in a simple configuration that consists of a single magnetic barrier region that is under uniaxial strain. The achieved polarization ($\approx 99\%$) is higher than the previous valley filtering works exploiting tunneling transport. We also introduce a solution to a major problem of similar valley filters, i.e., low conductance at high polarization regime. In the second section, dual spin-valley polarization is investigated in a strained silicene heterojunction. The buckled physical structure and relatively larger spin orbit-coupling in silicene allow us to apply spin-dependent potential via exchange interaction induced by the adjacent magnetic insulator layer. In addition to the exchange interaction, a uniaxial strain is applied locally within the first barrier region to generate valley polarization. Thus, all four combinations real spin and valley spin can be separated in angular space. To perform filtering operation, an additional electro-magnetic barrier is used to extract the desired spin-valley combination from the corresponding portion of the angular space.

In Chapter 4, Klein tunneling transmission is investigated in Weyl semimetals first time. Unlike graphene, the angular dependence of tunneling probability shows perfect transmission rings that are formed due to the resonance of electron waves in the barrier

region. The influence of magnetic field on the transmission is investigated. The shift of the perfect transmission angles is observed due to the transverse Lorentz displacement.

In Chapter 5, we study the effect of tilted energy dispersion which reveals an exotic transport phenomena such as the asymmetric refractions and reflections at the barrier interface, experienced by incident electrons, due to the coupling of electrical potential change and the tilt of the Weyl cone. Remarkably, the anomalous transverse shift has an effect on transmission analogous to magnetic barriers.

In Chapter 6, we utilize the tilt induced transverse shift presented in Chapter 5 and design a conductance modulation application in Weyl semimetals. The results show that a large conductance gap can be obtained with the aid of tilted dispersion and magnetic barriers. The effect of the temperature on the conductance profile is also investigated.

In Chapter 7, we study the tilt effect on the tunneling transport in the presence of a single pair of Weyl nodes that are related by inversion symmetry, which is the simplest Weyl semimetal phase, and show that the tilt induced anomalous transverse momentum shift that is presented in chapter 5 is a valley dependent feature. In this Chapter, study of our proposed electrically tunable valley filter is presented. The transport mechanisms are investigated regarding various aspects including Fermi surface orientation, effect of finite thickness of the device, detections of the generated valley polarization, existence of multiple pairs of Weyl nodes, and importance of k -space separation of Weyl nodes.

Finally, we give conclusions of the above works and emphasize the importance of the tilted dispersion in tunneling devices including p-n-p (n-p-n) junctions. We summarize the proposed applications and recommend possible further developments and applications based on the works presented in this Thesis.

TUNNELING TRANSPORT

2.1 Electrical properties of graphene and silicene

Transport mechanisms in condensed matter materials highly depend on the electrical properties of the host material. Obtaining energy momentum dispersion relation of a specific material is a crucial step in investigating the electrical transport properties, and how extrinsic or intrinsic factors can affect them. Here, we give a brief introduction on the electronic band structure calculations in graphene and silicene, which will be extended to three dimensional Weyl and Dirac semimetals in the following sections. To prepare the basis for subsequent sections, we introduce and analyze several means of modulating electrical transmission, such as mechanical strain, electrical barriers, magnetic barriers, spin-orbit coupling, and exchange interaction.

2.1.1 Electrical band structure

Tight-binding method is commonly used to calculate the electrical band structure of crystals [30, 38]. Graphene possesses periodic lattice structure, in which two carbon atoms form a unit cell. Since the energy levels corresponding to the $2s$, $2p_x$, $2p_y$ bands are far below or far above the Fermi energy, it is sufficient to take consideration only

Tunneling transport

the $2p_z$ orbital to investigate electrical properties of graphene [38]. Considering every unit cell and their neighbors, the system can be described by the following Hamiltonian [38];

$$\begin{pmatrix} 0 & h_0 \\ h_0^* & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (2.1)$$

where $h_0 = -t(1 + 2e^{-ik_x a} \cos(k_y b))$, b and a are lattice constants, t is the local hopping energy between two carbon atoms. Eigen-energies of the Hamiltonian (Eq. 2.1) are given by

$$E = \pm t \sqrt{1 + 4 \cos(k_y b) \cos(k_x a) + 4 \cos^2(k_y b)}. \quad (2.2)$$

The full band structure is shown in Fig. 2.1, which is calculated by Eq. 2.2. As shown in the band structure, valance and conduction bands touch each other at six Dirac points at $E = 0$ in the absence of external effects. Thus, there would be six valleys which belong to two inequivalent classes, i.e., K and K' .

The Fermi level is situated at $E = 0$ where the conduction and valence bands touch each other. Only the states in the range of a few $k_B T$ below or above Fermi level contributes to the conductance (k_B is Boltzmann constant, and T is temperature in Kelvin) [38]. Energy disperses linearly around Dirac point, which significantly reduce the complexity of the system if one focus on the low energy to predict electrical transport properties in graphene. The expansion near one of the Dirac points gives the low energy Hamiltonian as

Fig. 2.1 Full band structure of graphene from different view points. K and K' correspond inequivalent valleys at the six corner of the Brillouin zone.

$$H = \hbar v_F(\sigma \cdot \mathbf{k}). \quad (2.3)$$

The above result shows linear energy-momentum relation near Dirac points, which implies that the effective mass of electrons on graphene is zero. In the low energy range, the energy only depends on Fermi velocity (v_F), i.e., analogous to speed of light (c) in low energy range.

Similar to graphene, silicene has honeycomb lattice formed by silicon atoms [39]. Electrical structure also shows similar characteristic due to the similar crystal structure. Silicene lattice shows slightly buckled structure, where there is a small out-of-plane displacement between two neighboring atoms, i.e., so-called A and B sublattices. Due to the buckled physical structure, the equivalence of the sublattice A and B is lifted, which results in a finite energy gap. Unlike graphene, silicene possesses large spin orbit coupling (SOC) that is enough to lift the valley and spin degeneracy when the Fermi level is close to the Dirac point. This enables the use of real spin degree of freedom in various kind of applications such as spin-valley filters demonstrated in the

following sections. Due to the above reasons, silicene has attracted much attention both experimentally and theoretically. However, the experimental realization of silicene is a more difficult task as two-dimensional honeycomb structures require the sp^2 bond which is not common for silicon atoms [39].

2.1.2 Strain induced gauge fields in two-dimensional honeycomb lattices

The elastic physical structure of graphene elicits the question: how does stress and strain affect the electrical properties of the graphene? It has been shown that Dirac points shift in k -space when graphene is strained along particular directions [40]. The direction and the strength of the shift depend on the magnitude of the strain and its direction with respect to crystal axis [40]. The shift of the Dirac points causes a displacement of the Fermi surface, which in turn induces a significant effect on the electron transport especially when the shift occurs transverse to the transmission direction. Altering the electrical properties by applying mechanical strain is not exclusive to graphene but also occurs in similar hexagonal honeycomb lattices with similar crystal symmetry (e.g., silicene). Strain engineering is also applied in other condensed matter materials with different crystal symmetries (e.g., Weyl semimetals) to modulate electrical transport (e.g., Ref. [41]); however, it is not in the scope of this Thesis.

Without strain, the energy-momentum relation can be obtained by using the Hamiltonian (Eq. 2.3), and given by

$$E = \hbar v_F \sqrt{k_x^2 + k_y^2}. \quad (2.4)$$

The direction of the strain with respect to the crystal axis of the material is a crucial factor that determines the deformations on the band structure [40]. In the works presented in this Thesis, strain is utilized to lift the valley degeneracy by shifting Dirac points along the transverse direction. In the presence of applied uniaxial strain along the armchair direction (k_x), the transverse wave vector k_y will transform such as $k_y \rightarrow k_y \pm A_S$, where A_S is strain-related momentum shift of which sign depends on the valley index.

2.2 Electrical potential barriers

Electrical potential barrier refers to a high potential region that restricts the electron movement in one or more dimensions. From the view of classical physics, a particle cannot penetrate through a potential barrier. However, in quantum physics, there is a possibility that an electron can transmit across a potential barrier region, and this phenomenon is known as quantum tunneling. In this Thesis, we focus on the tunneling transmission in Dirac and Weyl semimetals, where the quasiparticles exhibit Weyl or Dirac fermion characteristics. In this section, we present basic tunneling examples in graphene. Later we will extend our calculations to other systems with specific configurations.

2.2.1 Single tunneling barrier

Two-dimensional materials such as graphene and silicene allow tuning the carrier concentration by electrical gates on top of the material surface [42]. A single one-dimensional barrier in graphene system is illustrated in the Fig. 2.2, where the electrical potential increased by V_0 within the central region with length L . The eigenfunctions of Eq. 2.3 are

Fig. 2.2 Illustration of a single potential barrier in graphene. Electrical gate increases the carrier concentration within the barrier region by V_0 . The length of the barrier region is denoted by L .

$$\psi_\eta \equiv \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} e^{i\vec{k}\vec{r}} \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ \eta e^{i\phi} \end{pmatrix} \equiv \begin{pmatrix} \psi_a \\ \psi_b^\eta \end{pmatrix} \quad (2.5)$$

where $\eta = \text{sgn}(E_F - V_0)$ is band index. Considering transmission along x -direction, and the boundary relations at $x = 0$ and $x = L$, the top component of the pseudospin ψ_a is

$$\Psi_a(x, y) = \begin{cases} (e^{ik_x x} + r e^{-ik_x x}) e^{ik_y y}, & x < 0, \\ (a e^{iq_x x} + b e^{-iq_x x}) e^{ik_y y}, & 0 < x < L, \\ t e^{ik_x x} e^{ik_y y}, & x > L. \end{cases} \quad (2.6)$$

The wave vectors are

$$\begin{aligned} k_x &= k_F \cos \phi, \\ k_y &= k_F \sin \phi, \end{aligned} \quad (2.7)$$

2.2 Electrical potential barriers

where $k_F = E_F/(\hbar v_F)$. The Fermi velocity (v_F) is equal to $c/300$ approximately [43]. k_y is a good quantum number, while k_x transforms in the barrier region as $k_x \rightarrow q_x$, i.e., given by

$$q_x = \sqrt{\frac{(E_F - V_0)^2}{\hbar^2 v_F^2} - k_y^2}. \quad (2.8)$$

Using the relation shown in Eq. 2.5, the lower component of the wave function ψ_b is given by

$$\Psi_b(x, y) = \begin{cases} (e^{ik_x x} e^{i\phi} + r e^{-ik_x x} e^{-i\phi}) e^{ik_y y}, & x < 0, \\ (a e^{iq_x x} \eta e^{i\theta} + b e^{-iq_x x} \eta e^{-i\theta}) e^{ik_y y}, & 0 < x < L, \\ t e^{ik_x x} e^{i\phi} e^{ik_y y}, & x > L. \end{cases} \quad (2.9)$$

The $1/\sqrt{2}$ factor can be neglected as it applies equally to both components of the wave function. The propagation angle θ can be found by considering the conservation of transverse momentum along the system, i.e., derived from

$$E_F \sin \phi = (E_F - V_0) \sin \theta. \quad (2.10)$$

Matching of the above wave functions at the barrier boundaries, the reflection coefficient r can be analytically found [10], which leads the transmission probability $T = |t|^2$. Using the relation of the wave vector components, transmission probability T can be derived as a function of the incident angle ϕ which is the angle between k_F and the transmission direction. The reflection coefficient is given by

$$r = -\frac{2i e^{i(Lq_x + \phi)} \sin(Lq_x) (\eta \sin(\theta) - \sin(\phi))}{e^{2iLq_x} (\eta \cos(\theta - \phi) - 1) + \eta \cos(\theta + \phi) + 1}. \quad (2.11)$$

Analyzing the above equation, one can find that $T(\phi) \rightarrow 1$ when $\phi = 0$, which means normal incident electrons can transmit perfectly due to the Klein tunneling [10]. The

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other significant point is that perfect transmission ($T = 1$) occurs only at $\phi = 0$ in the case of $V_0 \sim E_F$. As shown in the Fig. 2.3, $T \neq 0$ in both cases where $V_0 < E_F$ and $V_0 > E_F$. When the V_0 is close to E_F , possible transmission angles are squeezed around normal incidence ($\phi = 0$).

Fig. 2.3 Angular dependence of transmission probability across a single electrical barrier for different values of barrier heights, i.e., 10 meV, 90 meV, and 150 meV. The Fermi energy $E_F=100$ meV and barrier length $L=100$ nm, and Fermi velocity $v_F=10^6$ m/s.

2.2.2 Double tunneling barrier

In the above, electrical potential barrier height (V_0) is a tunable factor that can modulate the electron transmission in the device. Increasing the number of barriers enhances the controllability of the transport properties in such systems. The double potential barrier problem can be solved analytically as follows.

2.2 Electrical potential barriers

Considering the Eq. 2.5, incident and propagating waves in the second barrier region is given by

$$\Psi'_a(x, y) = \begin{cases} (te^{ik_x x} + r'e^{-ik_x x})e^{ik_y y}, & L < x < L'_1, \\ (a'e^{iq'_x x} + b'e^{-iq'_x x})e^{ik_y y}, & L'_1 < x < L'_2, \\ t'e^{ik_x x}e^{ik_y y}, & x > L'_2, \end{cases} \quad (2.12)$$

$$\Psi'_b(x, y) = \begin{cases} (te^{ik_x x}e^{i\phi} + r'e^{-ik_x x}e^{-i\phi})e^{ik_y y}, & L < x < L'_1, \\ (a'e^{iq'_x x}\eta e^{i\theta'} + b'e^{-iq'_x x}\eta e^{-i\theta'})e^{ik_y y}, & L'_1 < x < L'_2, \\ t'e^{ik_x x}e^{i\phi}e^{ik_y y}, & x > L'_2. \end{cases} \quad (2.13)$$

In the above, note that the transmission function t in the first barrier region is the coefficient of incident wave in the second barrier. L'_1 and L'_2 correspond to the length at the interfaces of the second barrier, and $L < L'_1 < L'_2$. Assuming the potential barrier height in the second barrier is V'_0 , the wave vector along the transmission is given by

$$q'_x = \sqrt{\frac{(E_F - V'_0)^2}{\hbar^2 v_F^2} - k_y^2}. \quad (2.14)$$

The transverse wave vector is a good quantum number in the whole system, and thus the propagation angle of electrons within the second barrier can be found by using

$$E_F \sin \phi = (E_F - V'_0) \sin \theta'. \quad (2.15)$$

Similar to the steps presented above for a single barrier, matching of the wave functions at the interfaces of two different barriers leads transmission probability $T'(\phi) = |t'|^2$. In a similar manner, more barriers can be included; however, the complexity would increase with the number of barriers. In the case of constant V_0 for all barriers along

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the system, different approaches can be applied to simplify the calculations based on the existent periodicity [30]. The above calculations form the basis of the tunneling solutions in this Thesis, as maximum two barrier systems are investigated.

2.2.3 Experimental realization of electrical potential barriers

Applying potential barriers means inducing localized change of the carrier concentration. The realization of the potential barriers depends on the physical and electrical properties of the target material. The most traditional way to increase carrier concentration is localized chemical doping, which is commonly used in semiconductor-based technologies.

In two-dimensional materials such as graphene, the carrier concentration can be effectively tuned by applying a gate voltage, where the gate is separated from the graphene layer by an insulating layer [42]. Similar to graphene, in three-dimensional Weyl and Dirac semimetals, carrier concentration (and hence the barrier height) can be tuned by applying a potential on a gated region or by regional alkali metal doping [44, 45]. By changing the carrier concentration locally, one can create Weyl semimetal system with approximately square shape band profile. Another option is to apply a back gate voltage to tune the Fermi level, and a top gate to change carrier concentration locally [44]. This method requires a quite thin sample (several nanometer thickness) because screening effect is only effective over short ranges. Another requirement is that the sample must reach sufficient thickness to allow the formation of Weyl nodes in the bulk. For instance, gate bias tuning of the carrier concentration of bulk states has been demonstrated in 50-nm thick Cd_3As_2 [44] and 14-nm thick WTe_2 [46].

2.2.4 Coherence length and mean free path

The tunneling transport has been realized in graphene and other 2D materials due to their long coherence length and mean free path (up to $\approx 5 \mu\text{m}$ in graphene [47]).

Similar to 2D materials, some of the recent Weyl semimetal candidates show very high mobility and large mean free path, e.g., $\approx 100 \mu\text{m}$ in WP2 [48], $\approx 5.2 \mu\text{m}$ in TaAs [49]. Even though some of them possess shorter mean free path, e.g., $\approx 100 \text{ nm}$ in Cd3As2 [50], the required channel length is achievable with current nanofabrication technologies. Coherent length is another factor that affect the tunneling transport, but it is generally larger than elastic mean free path [51] at low temperatures. Besides, wider device thickness is preferable in order to achieve coherent transport [47].

2.3 Magnetic tunneling barriers

2.3.1 Physical structure of magnetic barriers

External magnetic fields play a crucial role in manipulating both magnetic and electrical properties of a material. Here, we focus on the magnetic barriers and their effect on tunneling properties in the context of Dirac/Weyl materials.

Fig. 2.4 Physical structures of different types of magnetic barriers. (a) and (b) illustrate deposited Ferromagnetic (FM) layers on top of the target material. (c) shows a patterned superconductor layer that masks the applied magnetic field. (d) shows the uniform magnetic field applied directly to the target material.

Magnetic barriers can be achieved by using different physical structures. The most basic one is uniform magnetic field applied directly to the target material, which

is shown in Fig. 2.4 (d). In some cases, localized magnetic fields that produces a particular B-field profile are required. To apply localized B-field, ferromagnetic (FM) materials can be deposited on top of the target material [29, 52–56] as shown in Fig. 2.4 (a) and (b). In this case, there must be a dielectric layer between FM layer and the target material to avoid induced magnetization due to the proximity effect. The thickness of the dielectric layer must be as small as possible to generate a sharp B-field profile, as we would discuss in Chapter 7. The gauge field that electrons experienced is highly dependent on the magnetic anisotropy of the FM layer. A desired magnetic field profile can also be achieved by depositing superconductor layer on top of the target material [54, 57, 58] and applying uniform magnetic field.

2.3.2 Square-shape magnetic gauge potential

Square shape B-field profile is commonly assumed in electrical transport calculations due to its simplicity. As briefly described in the previous sections, spike-like magnetic fields are experimentally achievable. Here we describe such systems and analyze their transport properties. Fig. 2.5 (a) shows two asymmetric magnetic fields $\pm B_0(z)$ induced by one of the methods shown in Fig. 2.4 (a-c). The electrons would effectively experience the gauge potential $A_{(x)}$. The B-field profiles can be approximately described by two asymmetric delta magnetic fields $B_{z(x)} = B_0[\delta(x) - \delta(x-L)]$ along the z -direction [24, 26, 27, 59]. By the choice of the Landau gauge, the delta magnetic fields give rise to a piecewise constant magnetic vector (gauge) potential $\vec{A}_B = B_0 l_B [\Theta(x) - \Theta(x-L)] \hat{y}$, where l_B is magnetic length. The transverse wave vector experience a shift such as $k_y \rightarrow k_y + eA_B/\hbar$ within the barrier region. By considering both electrical and magnetic barriers, the momentum along the transmission direction within the barrier is given by

$$q_x = \sqrt{\frac{(E_F - V_0)^2}{\hbar^2 v_F^2} - (k_y + \delta k_y)^2} \quad (2.16)$$

Fig. 2.5 Magnetic field and gauge barrier profiles for (a) spike-like B-field induced by FM layers such as shown in Fig. 2.4 (a-c), and (b) uniform B-field that gives rise to linearly increasing gauge field.

where $\delta k_y = eA_B/\hbar$. Due to the conservation of energy and transverse momentum, electrons experience refractions at the barrier interface, and the propagation angles of the transmitted electrons are given by $\theta = \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{k_y}{q_x} \right)$ within the barrier region.

The angular shift of perfect transmission angles is shown in Fig. 2.6 for varying strengths of the delta function magnetic field. The above solution is sufficient to obtain the transmission and conductance profile in such systems as the magnetic field profile (the shape of the applied field) is not as important as magnetic barrier height, i.e., the

Fig. 2.6 Angular dependence of transmission probability across a potential barrier with height $V_0=30$ meV under influence of different strengths of delta function magnetic fields. The Fermi energy $E_F=100$ meV and barrier length $L=100$ nm, and Fermi velocity $v_F=10^6$ m/s.

maximum point of A_B . We will discuss this point for specific applications in the rest of the Thesis, and consider more realistic magnetic barrier profiles.

2.3.3 Uniform magnetic barriers

In the presence of a uniform magnetic field, a linearly changing gauge potential occurs as shown in the Fig. 2.5 (b). Such a magnetic field can be modeled by a piecewise constant function $\vec{B}_{0(z)} = B_0[\Theta(x) - \Theta(x - L)]\hat{z}$. Thus, the gauge potential is given by $\vec{A}_B = B_0x\hat{y}$. In this case, the analytical solution is not as easy as that shown in the previous section. Therefore, it is more convenient to solve the problem numerically by dividing the whole device into short segments where the magnetic gauge potential is spatially varying along x , and applying the transfer matrix method (Ref. [30]). As shown in the Fig. 2.7, the uniform magnetic field shifts the perfect transmission angles, which is similar to the shift shown in Fig. 2.6.

Fig. 2.7 (b) shows the angular dependence of transmission probability of the system illustrated in (a) where the potential barrier height is $V_0=200$ meV. Different colors show different magnetic field strengths. The Fermi energy $E_F=50$ meV, and Fermi velocity $v_F=2 \times 10^5$ m/s.

2.4 Tunneling conductance

2.4.1 Ballistic and diffusive transport

Electrical current can be characterized into two groups, i.e., drift and diffusion current based on Drude's model [60]. Drift current refers to the charge current induced by an electrical field applied to the system, where the carriers gain a particular drift velocity, i.e., a function of mobility and electrical field intensity. Diffusion current refers to the charge current due to the gradient of spatial distribution of the charge carriers, in the absence of electrical bias. This can be understood by the tendency of the carriers to flow from the high concentration region to low concentration region. In these models, carriers are subject to certain scattering mechanisms that determine the mobility of the system, which is a material property.

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Ballistic transport is defined as charge current in the absence of scattering factors. Scattering mechanisms play a minimal role in nanoelectronic systems as the current nano-fabrication technologies allow us to fabricate highly clean materials with minimal defects. As this Thesis focuses on the quantum mechanical transport properties of nanoelectronic materials, we would assume ballistic transport in the following sections unless otherwise stated.

2.4.2 Quantum conductance

Consider one-dimensional wire connected to two reservoirs with chemical potential μ_s and μ_d . In the case of perfect match between the energy of the electrons and Fermi energy, the density of states is given by $DOS=dn/hv$ where n is the number of electrons, h is Plank constant, and v is velocity. The voltage is $V = (\mu_s - \mu_d)/e$, where e is the electron charge. The current density is given by $j = -ev(\mu_s - \mu_d)DOS$. Thus, the conductance can be found as $G_0 = 2e^2/h$. The quantum conductance is highly dependent on the material properties, electrical band structure of the material, as well as the number of conducting channels. We will derive G_0 for specific systems and conditions in the following sections.

2.4.3 Landauer-Büttiker formalism

In the previous sections, transmission probability T is related to wave function matching between different regions, which is related to the refractions and reflections along the system. The total conductance of the system can be derived based on T by considering all possible transverse modes. In this Thesis, we define the transverse modes in terms

of incident angle ϕ in order to calculate the angular dependence of transmission. Based on the quantum conductance described previously, total current can be written as

$$I = \frac{2e}{h} \int dE M(E) (\mu_s - \mu_d) \quad (2.17)$$

where $M(E)$ is the number of modes, which is directly relate to the energy-momentum dispersion relation $E(k)$ [30, 38]. For specific material and dimensions, $M(E)$ can be estimated by

$$M(E) = \frac{\langle v_x \rangle h \text{DOS}(E)}{2L}. \quad (2.18)$$

Considering a single mode, Landauer-Büttiker equation reads

$$I = \frac{G_0}{e} \int dE T(E) (\mu_s - \mu_d) \quad (2.19)$$

where $T(E)$ is the transmission probability, which is equal to 1 in ballistic systems. In the following sections, detailed derivations of the above equations are presented according to specific system parameters.

3.1 Valley dependent tunneling transport in graphene

3.1.1 Introduction

The strain effect on two-dimensional hexagonal lattices is briefly described in the previous section. One of the interesting outcomes of applied strain is the shift of Dirac points, i.e., K and K' [40]. As the valley is a spin-like feature, generating and manipulating valley current is an essential requirement in realizing valleytronic applications [40]. The flexible structure of graphene allows the application of strain. The application of strain breaks the symmetry of coupling strengths between carbon atoms; therefore, an effective valley dependent potential occurs. So far, several valley filter applications have been proposed in two-dimensional materials [18, 24, 61, 62]. The first step to generate a valley polarization is breaking of inversion or time-reversal symmetry. This can be achieved by using uniform or time-dependent magnetic fields [63]. It has been shown that line defects can be used to generate valley polarized current [64]. Valley polarization can also be achieved by valley selective barrier structures [24, 62]. In general, the generated polarization is not 100% [62]; however, very high polarization can be achieved by optimizing the system parameters such as strain and

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magnetic field [24]. However, all previously proposed schemes mentioned above have a common drawback, i.e., low conductance at the high valley polarization regime.

The previously proposed schemes focus on two-barrier structures, where incident electrons are polarized in angular space at the first barrier interface, before being filtered out at the second barrier interface. Here, we combine two barrier structure into a single barrier. The advantage of doing this is not only the simpler barrier structure, but also the ability to achieve high conductance simultaneously with high valley polarization. Thus, the present valley filter proposal faces a general problem of maintaining a high conductance while at the same time achieving a high valley-polarization of current, the twin requisites for an efficient valley filter.

3.1.2 Theory

The use of potential barriers is one of the common ways to achieve electron filtering. Based on the wave nature of the electrons, refractions and reflections occur at the barrier interface. Consequently, there is a decrease in the conductance of system due to the reflected electrons. The present filter scheme aims to overcome this issue and realize a filter operation with maximum conductance, and zero reflection of electrons belonging to the desired valley. Besides, we also aim to achieve this by using parameters for strain and the magnetic field which are practically accessible. Basically, the proposed filtering method is based on using two external factors. The first one is the strained region to lift the valley degeneracy and spatially split the electrons of different valleys to opposite directions transverse to the transmission direction. Based on the conservation of energy and transverse momentum, we can achieve a situation of no overlap in spatial (angular) space between the transmission angles of the two valleys. The second one is the magnetic field to select the desired valley by breaking the angular symmetry of the transmission, which results in a total reflection of the electrons around one of the

3.1 Valley dependent tunneling transport in graphene

valleys. We integrate these two effects into a single barrier region which is perfectly transparent for the selected valley, and totally opaque for the other.

Fig. 3.1 Schematic illustration of the proposed valley filter, where the central region is under uniaxial strain applied along transmission (x -direction). In three distinct regions, electron wave functions are denoted by ψ_1 , ψ_2 , and ψ_3 . Two asymmetric ferromagnetic strips with perpendicular magnetic anisotropy are placed at the barrier boundaries.

3.1.2.1 Model and Hamiltonian

The proposed system is illustrated in Fig. 3.1; the uniform uniaxial strain field is applied in the barrier region, while a magnetic barrier is generated by means of two δ -function magnetic fields created by ferromagnetic stripes situated at the boundaries of the barrier region. The low energy Hamiltonian of graphene under uniaxial strain in the x -direction (armchair direction) and the magnetic field can be written by

$$H = \hbar v_F \hbar \boldsymbol{\sigma} \cdot (\mathbf{k} + \eta (v_F \hbar)^{-1} \mathbf{A}_S + \alpha (v_F \hbar)^{-1} \mathbf{A}_B) \quad (3.1)$$

where $\eta = \pm 1$ corresponds to the valley index, σ is Pauli matrixes in two dimensions, and $\alpha = \pm 1$ is related to the sign of the applied magnetic field. Uniaxial strain affects the hopping energy such that $t \rightarrow t + \eta \delta t_S$ where $t \approx 3$ eV. Thus, the electrons experience a gauge potential, i.e., $A_S = \delta t_S \hat{y}$. There is another gauge potential related to the ferromagnetic strips at the barrier boundaries, which can be defined as

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$\vec{A}_B = B_0 l_B [\Theta(x) - \Theta(x - L)] \hat{y}$. Applying the boundary conditions, and using the wave functions shown in Eq. 2.5, two spinor components are given by

$$\Psi_a(x, y) = \begin{cases} (e^{ik_x x} + r e^{-ik_x x}) e^{ik_y y}, & x < 0, \\ (a e^{iq_x x} + b e^{-iq_x x}) e^{ik_y y}, & 0 < x < L, \\ t e^{ik_x x} e^{ik_y y}, & x > L, \end{cases} \quad (3.2)$$

$$\Psi_b(x, y) = \begin{cases} (e^{ik_x x} e^{i\phi} + r e^{-ik_x x} e^{-i\phi}) e^{ik_y y}, & x < 0, \\ (a e^{iq_x x} \eta e^{i\theta} + b e^{-iq_x x} \eta e^{-i\theta}) e^{ik_y y}, & 0 < x < L, \\ t e^{ik_x x} e^{i\phi} e^{ik_y y}, & x > L. \end{cases} \quad (3.3)$$

In the above, the wave vectors are

$$\begin{aligned} k_x &= k_F \cos \phi, \\ k_y &= k_F \sin \phi. \end{aligned} \quad (3.4)$$

Within the barrier region, transverse wave vector transforms such as

$$k_y = \frac{\sin \theta E_F + \eta \delta t_S + \alpha A_B}{v_f \hbar} \quad (3.5)$$

where $\alpha = \pm 1$ depending on the sign of the magnetic field ($B_{0(z)}$). Using the conservation of transverse wave vector k_y , the propagation angle of electrons within the barrier is given by

$$\theta = \sin^{-1} \left(\frac{\sin \phi E_F + \eta \delta t_S + \alpha A_B}{E_F} \right). \quad (3.6)$$

Using the boundary conditions, and matching of the wave functions at the barrier interfaces, angular dependence of transmission probability $T(\phi)$ can be analytically calculated.

3.1.3 Results and discussions

3.1.3.1 Valley polarized transmission profile

We first analyze the effect of strain and magnetic barrier separately. In the proposed system, both factors lead step gauge barrier. The magnetic gauge barrier has the same influence on the all electrons based on transverse Lorentz displacement, while strain causes valley dependent transverse displacement. Therefore, magnetic barrier gives rise to shifted transmission angles along one of the transverse direction according to the sign of the applied field. Strain leads asymmetric refractions and reflections for electrons around different valleys at the barrier interface.

Fig. 3.2 The angular dependence of transmission probability $T(\phi)$ under the influence of (a) magnetic potential $A_B = 15$ meV, (b) strain gauge potential $\delta t_S = 15$ meV. The allowed transmission angles shifts by α in (a), while valley dependent shift occurs in (b)

The shift of the allowed transmission angles is shown in Fig. 3.2, which agrees with the analytic prediction shown in the previous sections. The one-directional shift induced by magnetic field and valley dependent shift induced by the strained region can be seen analytically in Eq. 3.5. We note that the strain and magnetic fields have antiparallel

Spin and valley dependent tunneling transport

(collinear) effects on the propagation direction of electrons for the $K(K')$ valley, as shown in Fig. 3.2. This means that there is no net gauge potential on the desired valleys (K) electrons, which can travel on without any deflection or reflection. For the other valley (K') electrons, the sum of the strain and magnetic gauge potentials causes an almost total reflection.

3.1.3.2 Valley polarized conductance profile

The valley dependent conductance can be calculated based on the transmission probability derived previously, such as

$$G_{K(K')} = G_0 \int_{-\pi/2}^{\pi/2} T(\phi) \cos \phi d\phi. \quad (3.7)$$

In the above, G_0 is quantum conductance and given by

$$G_0 = \frac{2e^2}{h} \frac{E_F W}{v_F \hbar} \quad (3.8)$$

where W is the width of the system. The valley polarization can be obtained by using the valley dependent conductance shown above. For instance, the polarization of K is

$$P_K = \frac{G_K - G_{K'}}{G_K + G_{K'}}. \quad (3.9)$$

The P_K is plotted in the Fig. 3.3 (a), which shows the polarization for varying magnetic and strain field for the case of barrier width $L = 100$ nm and Fermi energy $E_F = 25$ meV. The value of P_K approaches unity with increasing δt_S and A_B . The highest polarization is achieved when the gauge potential of magnetic field and strain, also the Fermi energy are equal to each other. The unit polarization is maintained when one or both of the magnetic and strain potentials exceed the Fermi energy. However, as shown in Fig. 3.3 (b), the conductance reaches the maximum only under the

3.1 Valley dependent tunneling transport in graphene

situation of equal magnetic and strain effect. This is because for a given magnetic field direction, the gauge potential of magnetic field would have the same sign and magnitude with one of the valleys, but of opposite sign with the other. For the latter, the two gauge fields cancel one another, as can be clearly seen from Eq. 3.5, which means perfect transmission for the selected valley (without any deflection). However, the same configuration results in an argument of arcsin that has a magnitude greater than 1 as the strain and magnetic gauge potentials have same sign (which corresponds to an imaginary ϕ), leading a total reflection of the corresponding valley. Note that, the relative difference between A_B and δt_S translates to inequality between ϕ and θ , hence results in a decrease in the conductance.

Fig. 3.3 (a) shows the polarization of the system for K . (b) is the total normalized conductance including the contribution of both valleys.

In the proposed scheme, the valley polarization exceeding 99% can be obtained for both valleys. Compared to the previously proposed valley filter in Ref. [24], which also shows high polarization, there is a marked difference in the conductance of the system. In the valley filter shown in Ref. [24], the conductance of the system is only $G_K = 0.31G_0$, which is quite lower than that achieved in the present system, i.e., $G_K \approx 2G_0$. Besides the only requirement of the proposed system is that the magnetic and uniaxial strain potentials must be matched with the Fermi energy. Therefore, the system does not require a specific range of parameters such as Fermi energy, which makes the system more versatile and practical. This also increases the experimental feasibility of our

proposed design, since one can potentially attain simultaneously high valley polarization and conductance with low magnetic and strain potential. The parameter values used in this work can be realized in current technology by applying magnetic field $B_0 \approx 1$ and strain 0.8% which have already been demonstrated experimentally [65–67].

3.1.4 Conclusions

In this section, we presented the generation of pure valley-polarized current by means of a single strained barrier region in monolayer graphene, where localized fringe magnetic fields are located at the barrier boundaries. The proposed valley filter is not confined to only particular values of strain and magnetic fields and does not come at the expense of high conductance. The only requirement for simultaneously achieving high valley filtering efficiency and high conductance is by matching both the strain and magnetic field gauge potentials to the Fermi energy. Besides, the single barrier set-up makes the proposed filter experimentally feasible. The theoretical calculations exhibit a very clear picture where combination of (i) uniaxial strain (i.e., to lift the valley degeneracy and shift the perfect transmission angles of the incident electrons to opposite transverse directions for different valleys), and (ii) applying a matching magnetic field (i.e., to shift the whole transmission profile due to the transverse Lorentz displacement) serves to block one of the valley spins from the transmission range (by total reflection), while aligning the other valley to the initial position (thus guaranteeing maximum transmission). Hence, the barrier becomes transparent for the electrons coming from the desired valley.

3.2 Spin-valley dependent transport in silicene

3.2.1 Introduction

As shown in the previous sections, graphene has been instrumental for many spintronic and valleytronic applications due to its unique band structure [31, 42]. In graphene, spin-orbit coupling (SOC) is negligibly small, which restricts the ability to control spin degree of freedom. Silicene shares the same monolayer-honeycomb structure as graphene, but having heavier silicon atoms and consequently larger spin-orbit coupling [68, 69]. Besides, silicene has been attracted attraction both theoretically [70] and experimentally [39] due to its unique electrical and transport properties, on account of its slightly buckled lattice. Like graphene, the inequivalent valleys K and K' at the corners of the reciprocal hexagonal lattice may be utilized in valleytronic applications by applying strain which distorts the coupling strengths within the honeycomb lattice. In practice, a controllable strain can be generated by depositing or transferring graphene onto stretchable substrates [66, 71]. Alternatively, such two-dimensional materials can be fabricated in the shape of free suspension across trenches [72].

As both real-spin and valley-spin degree of freedom is usable in silicene, it is possible to generate dual spin-valley polarized current. In the literature, such spin and valley polarized current has been achieved magneto-optically [73], electrically by means of a Y-shaped spin-valley device [74], by using two-dimensional U-shaped device [75], and a three-terminal Y-shaped spin separator [76]. The generation of spin-valley polarization by means of resonant tunneling scheme has also been proposed in silicene [77], which is effective only on normally incident electrons. Finally, a method [78] has been proposed to generate spin-valley current in silicene by application of electric field. However, the system is restricted to electron energy comparable to the SOC energy (of the order of a few meV).

3.2.2 Theory and model

In this section, we propose a silicene-based spin-valley filter consisting of a double-barrier structure, which can electrically generate highly-efficient ($> 90\%$) spin-valley polarization of current. The proposed scheme is not restricted to low electron energies of the order of the spin-orbit energy split Δ_{SOC} (a few meV) as that previously proposed spin-valley filters. The filtering is achieved based on i) strain and exchange field to carve out distinct spin-valley transmission angular profiles in momentum-space, and ii) magneto-electric fields in the second barrier to select the particular transmission lobe corresponding to the requisite spin-valley combination. Applying this method, one of the four combinations of spin-valley can be selected for transmission.

The proposed double barrier system is shown in Fig. 3.4. In the first barrier ($0 \leq x \leq L$), a uniform uniaxial strain is applied on the silicene lattice, and an exchange field is induced via adjacent magnetic insulators on top and below the silicene layer. In the second barrier ($L + a \leq x \leq 2L + a$), a pair of δ -function magnetic fields are located at the boundaries ($x = L + a$, and $x = 2L + a$) via two ferromagnetic (FM) stripes, and the electrical potential is modulated via top and bottom electrostatic gates. These two barrier regions take on different tasks: (i) the first region is utilized to create an angular separation (i.e., in ϕ -space, where ϕ is the angle of incidence) in the transmission of different spin and valley currents, while the second barrier region is used as a filter to cut off the desired combination of spin and valley via the transverse Lorentz displacement, and block all the others. In the below, these two regions are analyzed separately, and numerical analysis is carried out on both regions in an integrated manner to verify the analytical predictions.

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Fig. 3.4 Schematic illustration of double barrier silicene, where uniaxial strain is applied on the region donated by yellow surface and h_1, h_2 represent magnetic insulators (e.g., EuO) yielding to spin dependent energy gap in the region of $(0 \leq x \leq L)$. The second barrier consists of asymmetric FM stripes and electric potential barrier induced by top and bottom gates in the region of $(L + a \leq x \leq 2L + a)$. Both barrier length $L = 200$ nm and the gap between the barriers $a = 50$ nm.

3.2.2.1 Spin valley dependent transmission probability

Considering uniaxial strain in the x -direction and lattice-dependent exchange field, the low-energy Hamiltonian is given by

$$H_{\eta\sigma_z} = \hbar v_F (k_x \tau^x - \eta A_S k \tau^y) + \eta \sigma_z \Delta_{SOC} + \Delta_M + \mu_\sigma \quad (3.10)$$

where $\eta = \pm 1$ shows the valley index corresponding to valleys K and K' , respectively, σ_z is the Pauli matrix corresponding to real electron spin operator in the z -direction. As shown in Eq. 3.10, the intrinsic spin-orbit coupling energy term Δ_{SOC} couples the real and valley spin degrees of freedom. SOC energy is relatively small value of 3.9 meV in silicene [79]. Note that the external spin-orbit coupling (Rashba interaction) is not taken into account since it is very small compared to the other effects [80]. The electrical potential in Eq. 3.10 is defined by $\mu_\sigma = \mu_0 + \sigma \mu_M$, where μ_0 is the shift in the potential due to the application of the gate voltage (in the first barrier $\mu_0 = 0$), and μ_M is the contribution due to the exchange field, i.e., given by $\mu_M = \frac{1}{2} (h_1 + h_2)$,

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where $h_{1,2}$ are the exchange energies acting on the A and B sublattices of silicene. Here, the key part is the vertical separation of A and B sublattices with respect to one another, which is caused by the buckled physical structure of silicene. In addition to the spin-orbit interaction energy, there is an additional spin-dependent effect on the band gap of the system due to the exchange field, i.e., given by $\Delta_M = \frac{1}{2}(h_1 - h_2)\sigma_z$. This term is zero in the case of parallel magnetization of both the top and bottom magnetic insulators. Finally, application of strain in the x -direction possesses opposite effect on the local hopping energy, $t \rightarrow t + \delta t_S$ ($t \approx 1.6$ eV) [81] for bonds in the transverse y -direction. This leads to a strain gauge potential, i.e., $A_S = \delta t_S \hat{y}$.

In the first barrier region, the wave functions can be written as

$$\begin{aligned}
 \Psi_I(x) &= e^{ik_x x} \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ M_{\eta\sigma} e^{-i\eta\phi} \end{pmatrix} + R e^{-ik_x x} \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ -M_{\eta\sigma} e^{i\eta\phi} \end{pmatrix} & x < 0, \\
 \Psi_{II}(x) &= A e^{iq_x x} \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ N_{\eta\sigma} e^{-i\eta\theta} \end{pmatrix} + B e^{-iq_x x} \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ -N_{\eta\sigma} e^{i\eta\theta} \end{pmatrix} & 0 < x < L, \\
 \Psi_{III}(x) &= T e^{ik_x x} \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ M_{\eta\sigma} e^{-i\eta\phi} \end{pmatrix} & x > L.
 \end{aligned} \tag{3.11}$$

where $\sigma = \pm 1$ denote spin in the $\pm z$ direction. The coefficients in the above spinor expressions are given by

$$M_{\eta\sigma} = \frac{E + \eta\sigma\Delta_{SOC}}{\sqrt{E^2 - \Delta_{SOC}^2}}, \tag{3.12}$$

$$N_{\eta\sigma} = \frac{(E - \mu_\sigma) + \eta\sigma\Delta_{SOC}}{\sqrt{(E - \mu_\sigma)^2 - (\eta\sigma\Delta_{SOC})^2}}. \tag{3.13}$$

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The wave vectors can be defined in such a way that the x -component of these are given by $q_x = \sqrt{(E - \mu_\sigma)^2 - (\eta\sigma\Delta_{SOC})^2} \frac{\cos(\theta)}{\hbar v_F}$ and $k_x = \sqrt{E^2 - \Delta_{SOC}^2} \frac{\cos(\phi)}{\hbar v_F}$ within and outside of the barrier respectively. $\theta(\phi)$ is the angle between the Fermi wave vector k_F and x -direction within (outside) the barrier. Conservation of energy and transverse momentum leads

$$\sin(\phi)\sqrt{E^2 - \Delta_{SOC}^2} = \sin(\theta)\sqrt{(E - \mu_\sigma)^2 - (\eta\sigma\Delta_{SOC})^2} + \eta\delta t_S. \quad (3.14)$$

Based on the above equation, the propagation angle θ can be found as

$$\theta = \sin^{-1} \left(\frac{\sin(\phi)\sqrt{E^2 - \Delta_{SOC}^2} + \eta\delta t_S}{\sqrt{(E - \mu_\sigma)^2 - (\eta\sigma\Delta_{SOC})^2}} \right). \quad (3.15)$$

Finally, the matching of both component of the wave functions at the barrier boundaries gives the transmission probability $T = |T|^2$.

3.2.3 Results and discussions

3.2.3.1 Angular separation of four spin-valley combinations

We numerically calculate spin-valley resolved transmission probability $T(\phi)$. In Figs 3.5 (a) and (b), it appears that the angular transmission profile changes significantly when the strain and spin-dependent potential are varied. The dependence of $T(\phi)$ on the strain field δt_S can be explained as follows: In the presence of δt_S , the conservation of the transverse momentum at the interface between the unstrained and strained regions dictates that $E \sin(\phi) = E \sin(\theta) \pm \delta t_S$, and thus, $\sin(\theta) = \sin(\phi) \mp \frac{\delta t_S}{E}$. So that, the change in δt_S directly affects the allowed transmission angle of electrons. Besides, as also shown earlier, the momentum q_x is a function of spin-dependent potential μ_σ , which leads further angular separation of the transmission probability $T(\phi)$ for different spin orientations.

Fig. 3.5 Spin-valley resolved transmission probability where $E_F = 25$ meV, $L = 200$ nm, $a = 50$ nm, $\Delta_{SOC} = 3.9$ meV, a) polarization of different spin-valley in ϕ -space under the optimal configuration of strain and spin-dependent potential $\delta t_S = 43$ meV, $h_1 = h_2 = 2$ meV as a result of the first barrier b) angular dependence of transmission probability under non-optimal configuration of strain and spin-dependent potential $\delta t_S = 16$ meV, $h_1 = h_2 = 2.5$ meV. c), d), e) and f) show total transmission probability of the system after passing through the second region. The magnetic and electric potentials in the second region are set at the optimal value so as to achieve an effective filter operation for all four spin-valley combinations: c) K_{\uparrow} , d) K'_{\downarrow} , e) K_{\downarrow} , and f) K'_{\uparrow} . The magneto-electric configuration for the filter operations of the four spin-valley combinations are as follows: c) $\mu = 2$ meV and $\delta t_B = 43$ meV, d) $\mu = -2$ meV and $\delta t_B = -43$ meV, e) $\mu = -2$ meV and $\delta t_B = 43$ meV, f) $\mu = 2$ meV and $\delta t_B = -43$ meV.

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It can be seen that under certain configuration of strain and exchange strength in the first barrier, the allowed transmission angles of all spin-valley combinations diverges in the incident angular space ϕ . This is a prerequisite for highly-efficient filter operation in the second barrier region. As Klein tunneling transmission always allows transmission at normal incidence, i.e. $\sin(\theta) = 0$, the angles corresponding to perfect transmission for the two valleys can be found as $\phi = \eta \sin^{-1} \left(\frac{\delta t_S}{\sqrt{E^2 - \Delta_{SOC}^2}} \right)$. Hence, one observes that the separation of the K and K' valley polarization in ϕ -space is induced by the strain energy δt_S . In the case of finite barrier thickness, perfect transmission ($T = 1$) occurs under the resonance condition: $q_x L = n\pi$, where $n = 0, \pm 1, \dots$ [10]. For a sufficiently long device length, extra resonance peaks occur corresponding to $n \geq 2$. Besides, q_x depends on the real spin due to the spin-dependent potential μ_σ , which leads a further angular separation of the perfect transmission direction for opposite spins $\sigma = \pm 1$. These perfect transmission angles can be derived analytically for all four spin-valley combinations ($\sigma = \pm 1, \eta = \pm 1$) by considering both the resonance condition and the conservation of transverse momentum (Eq. 3.15). The above analytical analysis agrees with the location of the transmission peaks which are obtained numerically in Figs. 3.15 (a) and (b). In the case shown in Fig. 3.15 (a), the strain energy is chosen to be sufficiently large ($\delta t = 43$ meV) so that only the first resonant peak, i.e., $q_x L = \pm\pi$ is allowed, while the higher resonances correspond to angles greater than $\frac{\pi}{2}$ are totally reflected. Note that the strain energy cannot be excessively large; otherwise, this would totally suppress the conduction including the first resonant peak due to the conservation of transverse momentum.

Distinct angular separation of the transmission peaks for all spin-valley combinations is achieved in the first barrier region. Thus, we are in a position to effectively filter the desired spin-valley polarization by means of the second barrier. We use magnetic vector and electrical potentials to achieve the spin-valley filtering at the second barrier.

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Delta δ -function magnetic fringe fields $B_z(x) = B_0 l_B [\delta(x) - \delta(x - L)]$ are generated at the boundaries of the second barrier (here for simplicity we set $x=0$ at the left boundary) by antisymmetric ferromagnetic stripes (see Fig. 3.4), which yields a square-hat vector (gauge) potential $A_B = B_0 l_B [\Theta(x) - \Theta(x - L)] \hat{y}$ within the second barrier, where $l_B = \sqrt{\frac{\hbar}{eB_0}}$ is the magnetic length. Essentially, this gauge potential induces a transverse deflection of the electrons, thus allowing a certain angular range in ϕ -space to transmit through the second barrier. A_B should match the magnitude of the strain gauge A_S to achieve optimal valley polarization. Under this matching condition, the transverse deflection from the strain A_S and fringe field A_B cancels one another, allowing electrons of the particular valley index η to transmit through, which is similar to the valley filter application presented in the Section 3.1. Based on the matching condition $\eta \frac{\delta t_S}{v_F} = e B_0 l_B$, the required magnetic fringe field is given by $B_0 l_B = \eta \frac{1}{\hbar e} \left(\frac{\delta t}{v_F} \right)^2$. Similarly, the electrical potentials applied on the barrier regions should also be matched, i.e., $\mu_{\sigma,1} = \mu_{\sigma,2} \rightarrow \sigma \mu_{M,1} = \mu_{0,2}$, i.e., the electrical potential μ_0 (due to the gate bias in the second barrier) should be equal to the (exchange induced) spin-dependent potential $\sigma \mu_M$ (in the first barrier). Therefore, highly efficient filter operation can be achieved for the desired combination of spin (σ) and valley (η).

3.2.3.2 Filtering function for desired spin-valley

In our analytical treatment shown above, we have considered the two barrier regions separately. Here, we analyze the overall transmission probability of the whole system by considering the Dirac electrons in all five regions and apply the matching conditions at the barrier boundaries. Based on the $T(\phi)$, we calculate the spin-valley dependent conductance by integrating over the incident angles:

$$G_{K(K')}^{\uparrow(\downarrow)} = G_0 \int_{-\pi/2}^{\pi/2} T(\phi) \cos \phi d\phi \quad (3.16)$$

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where $G_0 = \frac{e^2}{h(E_F L_y / \hbar v_F)}$. Finally, the spin-valley polarization (e.g., for valley K and spin \uparrow) is defined by

$$P_{K\uparrow} = \frac{(G_{K\uparrow} - G_{K\downarrow}) + (G_{K\uparrow} - G_{K'\uparrow}) + (G_{K\uparrow} - G_{K'\downarrow})}{3(G_{K\uparrow} + G_{K\downarrow} + G_{K'\uparrow} + G_{K'\downarrow})}.$$

Based on the spin-valley separation at the first barrier region, the angular dependence of the whole system (transmission across all five regions) shows high filtering operation occurs at the first barrier as shown in Fig. 3.5 (c) to (f). In all four cases, we obtain transmission of the only desired spin-valley polarization while the other three spin-valley combinations are virtually filtered out, where $P_{\sigma,\eta} \geq 0.94$. To change the desired spin-valley polarization that the system generates, one can change the sign of the magnetic and electrical potentials in the second barrier, i.e., by reversing gate-induced potential $\mu_0 \rightarrow -\mu_0$ and the fringe magnetic field $B_z \rightarrow -B_z$.

In Fig. 3.5, we set the system parameters to optimal values that generate high polarization. To show the dependence of the polarization on the correlation of parameters, the valley-spin polarization $P_{K\uparrow}$ for the K valley and spin-up electrons is plotted over the range of strain field between 40 meV and 65 meV in Fig. 3.6 (a). The plot exhibits a peak at 43 meV, the value which matches the magnetic field strength in the second barrier (filter) region. Similarly, the polarization $P_{K\uparrow}$ decreases sharply due to the mismatch of the vector potentials A_S and A_B in the first and second regions in the case of strain values δt_S slightly above or below 43 meV. Interestingly, there is a reduction in the polarization $P_{K\uparrow}$ when both the strain δt and the exchange field $h_{1,2}$ (and hence the spin-dependent potential) are varied. This means an increasing strain can be counter-acted by reducing the exchange field [see Fig. 3.6 (b)]. This can be understood by considering the effects of these two parameters on the angular dependence of transmission probability simultaneously. As shown in Fig. 3.6 (c),

Fig. 3.6 The effect of varying strain field (Δt_S) and spin-dependent potential $h_{1,2}$ on the transmission $P_{K\uparrow}$. In the calculations, $E_F = 25$ meV, $L = 200$ nm, $a = 50$ nm, $\Delta_{SOC} = 3.9$ meV. (a) The polarization $P_{K\uparrow}$ as a function of the strain field which is varied between 40 meV and 65 meV; (b) The dependence of the polarization $P_{K\uparrow}$ on both the strain field and exchange field $h_{1,2}$; (c), (d), and (e) show the effect of changes in the strain field and the exchange field on the angular position of the peak transmission probability across the first region. The dashed black plot represents the angular position which matches the parameters (magnetic field and electrical potential) of the second barrier (filter) region.

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when we set $\delta t = 43$ meV and $h_{1,2} = 2$ meV, the peak of the transmission curve $T_{K\uparrow}$ (blue curve) exactly coincides with the black dashed line which denotes the angular orientation which matches the second filter region. However, a small change of δt_S to 44 meV, results in a significant shift in the transmission in ϕ -space [see Fig. 3.6 (d)] away from the dashed line. This translates into a drop in the transmitted spin-valley of (K, \uparrow) across the filter region, and hence a lower $P_{K\uparrow}$. However, by modifying the exchange field to $h_{1,2} = 1$ meV, the peak of the $T_{K\uparrow}$ curve can be made to coincide with the dashed line [see Fig. 3.6 (e)], and thus $P_{K\uparrow}$ is restored to its peak value. The required change in $h_{1,2}$ (dh) can be analytically derived by considering derivative of ϕ_p (i.e., the angle of the transmission peaks) with respect to δt_S and h_1, h_2 , which is given by

$$\frac{dh}{d\delta t_S} = \frac{\frac{\partial \phi_p}{\partial \delta t_S}}{\frac{\partial \phi_p}{\partial h}}. \quad (3.17)$$

In the above, the ϕ_p can be found by using the first transmission resonance peak based on $q_x L = \pm\pi$, and by substituting the related expressions. Solving the above equation, dh is approximately given by

$$dh \approx d\delta t_S \frac{\sqrt{L^2 \xi [-\hbar^2 v_F^2 \pi^2 + L^2 ((E_F - h_x)^2 - \Delta_{SOC}^2)]}}{L^2 (E_F - h_x) \sqrt{\xi}} \quad (3.18)$$

where $\xi = (E_F - \Delta_{SOC})(E_F + \Delta_{SOC})$ and $h_x = h_{1,2}$. The numerical result shown in Fig. 3.6 (c) to (e) are in agreement with the above analytical expression.

3.2.4 Summary and conclusions

In this section, we theoretically study the real and valley spin-polarized transport in a double-barrier system based on strained silicene, capable of achieving high polarization of current (exceeding 90%). The proposed spin-valley filter utilizes i) strain and

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exchange field in the first barrier to carve out distinct spin-valley transmission angular profiles in momentum-space, and ii) magneto-electric fields in the second barrier to select the requisite spin-valley combination and filter the others. The resultant spin-valley polarization has been demonstrated both analytically and numerically, which shows that almost pure spin-valley current can be realized based on geometric and material parameters that are within practical feasibility. In the numerical calculations, we assume a barrier width of $L = 200$ nm, and matching magnetic field strength of $B_0 = 1$ T and strain energy of $\delta t = 25$ meV. These parameter values are experimentally feasible, and thus the proposed spin-valley filter can be realized with current technology. By contrast, the spin-valley filtering solely by means of spin-orbit coupling effect [78] yields a much larger overlap of the transmission profiles of the different valleys and spins, which significantly reduces the achieved polarization. Besides, the valley-spin polarization occurs only at low electron energies, comparable to the SOC energy of a few meV's. Numerically, it was found that the SOC-induced valley and spin polarization attains a value of about 10% at electron energy of 10 meV, and vanishes when the energy is increased to 20 meV, as also extensively discussed in [78].

KLEIN TUNNELING IN WEYL SEMIMETALS

4.1 Introduction

The discovery of graphene has enabled experimental realization of Klein tunneling in accessible condensed matter systems [82–86]. Similar to graphene, Weyl semimetals exhibit zero energy gap between electron and hole states, which makes it a viable avenue for realizing three-dimensional relativistic electron transport. Unlike graphene, a Weyl fermion possesses three-dimensional energy dispersion in k -space. Weyl semimetals provide a stable topological state of which energy dispersion can be described by Weyl Hamiltonian (Eq. 4.1), which is

$$H = \hbar v_F \boldsymbol{\sigma} \cdot \mathbf{k} + V_0 = \hbar v_F (\sigma_x k_x + \sigma_y k_y + \sigma_z k_z) + V_0 \quad (4.1)$$

where v_F is the Fermi velocity, and σ represents all three Pauli matrices. Electronic states in Weyl semimetals consist of bulk states and Fermi arc states on the surface. The Weyl nodes in bulk always appear in pairs with opposite chirality where the sign of the velocity carries the chirality. Two Weyl nodes with opposite chirality are connected by Fermi arc states. The electronic band structure is highly robust as it contains all three Pauli matrices [87].

Due to the exotic electrical and magnetic properties of bulk and surface states, Weyl semimetals have attracted attention both theoretically and experimentally [88–91]. Recently, Fermi arc states have been observed in several materials such as TaP [92] and YbMnBi [93]. The bulk transport properties have also been studied both theoretically and experimentally [93–95]. Weyl semimetals show very high mobility with zero effective mass of electrons, which makes it a promising candidate for tunneling applications. So far, transport properties of Weyl semimetals have been investigated based on charge transport in the presence of Coulomb interactions or temperature dependent disorder [96], and magnetotransport using Boltzmann theory and assuming randomly distributed charge impurities [97]. It has been also shown that Weyl semimetals exhibit extremely large magnetoresistance and ultra high mobility [98].

4.2 Theory

Perfect transmission angles (i.e., so-called *magic* angles) refer to unit transmission angles and are the key evidence of the absence of backscattering in Dirac materials such as graphene [10]. They have been widely analyzed in context of graphene and silicene as presented in the previous sections. Here we analyze the magic angles in three dimensions in the presence and absence of magnetic fields induced by four ferromagnetic stripes, as shown in Fig. 4.1. Similar to graphene, our tunneling calculations are based on electron wave functions in three regions confirms the absence of backscattering for normally incident electrons in three-dimensional Weyl semimetals. Our results show that in the case of applied additional magnetic barriers, a particular wave vector can be selected by tuning the field strength and direction, which may be useful for electro-optic applications. The three-dimensional tunneling profile reveals that the resonance of k_F and the L gives rise to magic transmission rings, which are perfect transmission angles in two transverse dimensions.

4.2.1 Physical model of the proposed system

In the previous sections, electrical potential barrier structures are investigated in the context of graphene, where carrier concentrations can be easily tuned by gated potential due to the two-dimensional physical structure. Similar to graphene, there are several methods to modulate the carrier concentration in Weyl semimetals [see Section 2.2.4]. In this section, we consider a rectangular, one-dimensional potential barrier as shown in Fig. 4.1. In the case where the potential barrier height exceeds the Fermi energy, the Fermi level would cut across the conduction band in the first and third regions, but would lie within the valence band in the second region. In addition to the electrical barrier, ferromagnetic stripes are placed on top and one side of the Weyl semimetal at the barrier boundaries in the proposed scheme. The anti-symmetric configuration of magnetic anisotropy of the ferromagnetic stripes induces magnetic field B_z which can be modeled by a delta-function at the barrier interfaces [see Section 2.3]. This generates a magnetic gauge potential A_y as shown in Fig. 4.1 (b). Based on the configuration of ferromagnetic strips, two magnetic fields along y - and z -direction can be controlled independently, and hence the gauge potential on arbitrary transverse direction can be effectively generated.

4.2.2 Transmission probability across electrical potential barrier

Transmission probability can be obtained by using electron wavefunctions in the three regions, which are Ψ_1 , Ψ_2 and Ψ_3 for the incident, propagated, and transmitted electrons, respectively. In this section, we investigate the transport properties by considering Weyl electrons near one node and neglect the contribution of Fermi arcs and intervalley scattering to the conduction. We will later show that these factors

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have a negligible effect on the angular dependence of transmission probability (see the following sections).

Fig. 4.1 The proposed single barrier model based on Weyl semimetal under the influence of magnetic field induced by four ferromagnetic stripes on the top and one side surfaces. The anti-symmetric magnetic anisotropy of ferromagnetic stripes generates a magnetic field profile that can be approximately described by a delta function magnetic fields B_z and B_y . Gated potential barrier changes the carrier concentration of the central region, such that the Fermi level (blue dashed line) cuts across the conduction band in first and third regions, but lies within the valance band in the second region. The occupied states are represented by light blue regions near the Weyl nodes.

By solving the Hamiltonian Eq. 4.1, the eigenenergies are given by $E_F - V_0 = \pm \hbar v_F k_F$. The positive part represents the electron states while the negative part is for hole states. We consider electron transmission along x -direction at angles γ (the angle

between k_F and the xy plane) and ϕ (the azimuthal angle with respect to the x -axis), the components of the eigenstates of equation (4.1) are given by

$$\psi_{\pm} \equiv \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} e^{i\vec{k}\vec{r}} \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ e^{i\phi} \sec \gamma (\eta + \sin \gamma) \end{pmatrix} \equiv \begin{pmatrix} \psi_a \\ \psi_b^\eta \end{pmatrix}. \quad (4.2)$$

The wave function is composed of two spinor components ψ_a and ψ_b^η , where $\eta = \text{sign}(E_F - V_0)$ is the band index. The top component Ψ_a can be written for the incident, propagating and transmitted regions such as

$$\psi_a(x, y) = \begin{cases} (e^{ik_x x} + r e^{-ik_x x}) e^{ik_y y}, & x < 0, \\ (a e^{iq_x x} + b e^{-iq_x x}) e^{ik_y y}, & 0 < x < L, \\ t e^{ik_x x} e^{ik_y y}, & x > L. \end{cases} \quad (4.3)$$

Based on the relation $\psi_b = e^{i\phi} \sec \gamma (\eta + \sin \gamma) \psi_a$, the bottom component ψ_b is given by

$$\psi_b(x, y) = \begin{cases} (e^{ik_x x} e^{i\phi} \sec \gamma (1 + \sin \gamma) - r e^{-ik_x x} e^{-i\phi} \sec \gamma (1 + \sin \gamma)) e^{ik_y y}, & x < 0, \\ (a e^{iq_x x} \sec \alpha (\eta + \sin \alpha) e^{i\theta} - b e^{-iq_x x} \sec \alpha (\eta + \sin \alpha) e^{-i\theta}) e^{ik_y y}, & 0 < x < L, \\ t e^{ik_x x} e^{i\phi} \sec \gamma (1 + \sin \gamma) e^{ik_y y}, & x > L. \end{cases} \quad (4.4)$$

Note that we assume the Fermi energy to be always positive. In the above, the wave vectors are

$$\begin{aligned} k_x &= k_F \cos \gamma \cos \phi, \\ k_y &= k_F \cos \gamma \sin \phi, \\ k_z &= k_F \sin \gamma, \end{aligned} \quad (4.5)$$

where the Fermi wave-vector

$$k_F = (E_F - V_0) / \hbar v_F. \quad (4.6)$$

Inside the barrier, k_x transforms as

$$q_x = \sqrt{((E_F - V_0) / (\hbar v_F))^2 - k_y^2 - k_z^2}. \quad (4.7)$$

Based on the conservation of transverse momentum, the propagation angles of carriers within the barrier region are given by

$$\theta = \tan^{-1}\left(\frac{k_y}{q_x}\right), \quad (4.8)$$

$$\alpha = \tan^{-1}\left(\frac{k_x}{q_x}\right) \cos \theta. \quad (4.9)$$

Using the wavefunction continuity at the barrier boundaries transmission function t and hence angular dependence of transmission probability $T(\phi, \gamma)$ can be analytically calculated.

4.3 Results and discussions

4.3.1 Angular dependence of transmission probability

Here, we first analyze the transmission probability $T = |t|^2$ in the presence of different applied potential V_0 , where the Fermi energy is constant ($E_F \approx 82$ meV). In Fig. 4.2 (a) and (c), the angular dependence of the transmission probability is shown in the case where V_0 is much higher than E_F , which corresponds to the case where tunneling transmission occurs between electron and hole states at the barrier interface. As shown

in Fig. 4.2 (b) and (d), when the system is reduced in two dimensions by choosing constant zero for one of the incident angles ($\phi = 0$ or $\gamma = 0$), the transmission profile is exactly same as the graphene case previously presented in Ref. [10]. When the barrier height V_0 is comparable to E_F , only normal incident electrons ($\gamma \approx 0$ and $\phi \approx 0$) can transmit across the barrier perfectly. The resonance of Fermi wavevector k_F and the barrier length L give rise to the additional perfect transmission rings which can be derived by the resonance condition $q_x L = \pi n, n = 0, \pm 1, \dots$ (substituting the expression of q_x above).

In two-dimensional Dirac materials such as graphene and silicene, these resonances give rise to perfect transmission angles. Note that the analytical analysis given in Eq. 4.10 confirms the perfect transmission angles in Fig. 4.2 (b), (d) as well as Ref. [10]. Unlike graphene, Weyl semimetals show perfect transmission rings as a consequence of resonances conditions. As the momentum along the transmission q_x is a function of V_0 and E_F the number and shape of the rings can be predicted that they highly depend on applied voltage and Fermi energy. Besides, longer barrier length enables more transmission rings (see Fig 4.3). Analytically, these perfect transmission angles can be analytically predicted by using resonance conditions as

$$L \sqrt{\frac{(E_F - V_0)^2}{\hbar v_F} k_F^2 \sin^2(\gamma) - k_F^2 \cos^2(\gamma) \sin^2(\phi)} = \pi n, n = 0, \pm 1, \dots \quad (4.10)$$

An incident angle that satisfies the expression in Eq. 4.10 gives rise to a unit transmission probability ($T = 1$), i.e., denoted by bright pixels in Fig. 4.3. From practical point of view, the angular dependence of transmission in Fig. 4.3 may be observed by using a point electron source and performing measurement of electron transmission density at the second barrier interface.

Fig. 4.2 Transmission profile of electrons across a potential barrier for different configuration of applied potentials in the case of $L = 100$ nm and $E_F \approx 82$ meV. (a) and (c) show the cases of $V_0 \approx 200$ meV and 285 meV respectively. (e) shows the case when the applied potential is close to Fermi energy ($V_0 = 80$ meV), only normal incidence electrons can transmit as Fermi level is very close to the Weyl node in the barrier region. (b), (d) and (f) represent the cross section of three-dimensional transmission profile (a), (c) and (e) in the case of $\gamma = 0$.

Fig. 4.3 Angular profile of tunneling transmission in the case of $E_F \approx 82$ meV, $V_0 = 150$ meV for different configurations of the barrier length L . Larger barrier lengths result in more magic transmission rings, and the combination of the perfect incident angles for two transverse directions causes distinct transmission profiles.

4.3.2 Effect of magnetic field on the tunneling transmission

In this part, we analyze the angular dependence of transmission probability under the influence of magnetic field, i.e., induced by deposited ferromagnetic stripes on top and side of the surfaces. We assume delta-function magnetic field profiles at the barrier boundaries, which cause the gauge potentials (Eqs. 4.11 and 4.12) on both transverse directions, i.e., z - and y -directions. In the following sections, we will show that a more realistic magnetic field profile does not change the characteristic of the angular dependence of transmission profile.

$$A_y = B_z l_B [\Theta(x) - \Theta(x - L)] \hat{y}, \quad (4.11)$$

$$A_z = B_y l_B [\Theta(x) - \Theta(x - L)] \hat{z}, \quad (4.12)$$

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where $l_B = \sqrt{\frac{\hbar}{|e|B_0}}$. Thus, the Hamiltonian in Equation (4.1) must be rewritten as $H = v_F(\sigma \cdot (p + eA)) + V_0$. Note that Zeeman splitting is neglected as the energy shift is very small unless there is a very high magnetic field of ≈ 25 T applied, as shown experimentally in TaP in Ref. [99]. The magnetic fields in the proposed model cause a change on the both transverse wave vectors such as $k_y \rightarrow k_y + (eA_y)/\hbar$, $k_z \rightarrow k_z + (eA_z)/\hbar$. Thus, the transverse wave vectors transforms such as

$$k_y = \frac{E_F \cos \gamma \sin \phi + sv_F \sqrt{|B_y| \hbar |e|}}{\hbar v_F}, \quad (4.13)$$

$$k_z = \frac{E_F \sin \gamma + sv_F \sqrt{|B_z| \hbar |e|}}{\hbar v_F}, \quad (4.14)$$

where $s = \pm 1$ represents the sign of the magnetic field. The magnetic field vectors are independent and orthogonal to each other which can create an arbitrary direction magnetic field on the yz plane. As shown in the Fig. 4.4, the transmission profile is affected by the magnetic field due to the transverse Lorentz displacement. The angular dependence of transmission shows that a very small range of incident vector can be selected in two-dimensional transmission space by tuning the applied fields, i.e., modulating the magnetization of the ferromagnetic strips. The transmission rings are two-fold symmetric in the absence of magnetic field as shown in Fig. 4.3 (a), while they exhibit deflected and distorted profile under the influence of the magnetic field [see Figs. 4.4 (a) and (b)]. In the case where transmission is allowed only for normal incidence due to the comparable applied potential and the Fermi energy [see Fig. 4.2 (e)], a specific wavevector be chosen for unit transmission by tuning the magnetic gauge potentials as shown in Figs. 4.4 (c) and (d). The ability to choose a specific incident vector for unit transmission while blocking the other incident angles may be very useful

for electro-optic applications. Besides, the radius of this perfect transmission region can be tuned by changing the difference between E_F and V_0 .

Fig. 4.4 Angular profile of tunneling transmission under the influence of magnetic field by considering magnetic gauge potentials on z - and y -component of Fermi wavevector for barrier length $L = 100$ nm. (a) and (b) are the effect of magnetic field in the case of $V_0 = 140$ meV and $V_0 = 200$ meV respectively. (c) and (d) shows the effect of magnetic field on normal incident electrons where the barrier allows only normal incident electrons due to the applied potential, i.e., close to Fermi energy ($E_F \approx 82$ meV, $V_0 = 60$ meV).

4.3.3 Comparison of magnetic deflections in graphene and Weyl semimetals

As the low energy characteristic of energy-momentum dispersion relation in graphene and Weyl semimetals are similar, one can expect that the effect of an applied magnetic barrier in the central barrier region in graphene and Weyl semimetal would be similar. The results shown in Fig. 4.5 confirm that the application of magnetic barrier on graphene with the same barrier configurations shifts perfect transmission angles in a similar way, as occurred in Weyl semimetals. However, carriers are confined to two dimensions in graphene. There is no characteristic difference between two cases,

because Weyl semimetals shows linear energy dispersion in three dimensions at low energies, but graphene possesses linear dispersion in two dimensions. However, if one adds another layer to monolayer graphene that would change the linear band dispersion to quadratic in k as occurs in bilayer graphene. Also, other bands might emerge. These significantly change transport properties of the system.

Fig. 4.5 Angular profile of tunneling transmission in graphene where applied magnetic barrier gives rise to a constant vector potential in the barrier region, and induced by two asymmetric ferromagnetic strips at barrier boundaries for different electrical potential profiles (a) 285 meV, and (b) 63 meV, where the Fermi energy is 83 meV and barrier length is 100 nm.

4.3.4 Linear Hamiltonian validity in Weyl semimetals

In the proposed scheme, low energy excitation of carriers is sufficient to investigate the tunneling properties of Weyl semimetals. The Hamiltonian (Eq. 4.1) describes the dynamics of electrons near one Weyl node. The validity of low energy approximation is restricted by the energy range where the dispersion is linear. Recent works have shown that the linear energy dispersion along all three directions in Weyl semimetals is effectual up to 0.4 eV in NbAs [89]. Note that this result does not imply an upper

limit, and the Fermi energy used as example in the works presented in this Thesis is in the linear range. Additionally, the linear dispersion up to 2.5 eV has also been observed in Dirac semimetal Cd₃As₂ [45].

4.3.5 Magnetic barrier superlattices

In this section, we focus on tunneling transmission across a single magnetic barrier that induces a constant magnetic gauge potential as shown in Fig. 4.1 (b). Previous works [67, 100] have shown that magnetic barrier superlattice of two-dimensional Dirac semimetals yields very interesting phenomena, such as electron collimation and resonant tunneling transport. In our scheme, the momentum shift of electrons occurs due to the mismatch of the Fermi surfaces along the transmission direction. In the presence of magnetic superlattices, this mismatch would be cumulative through the lattice, and may induce different transmission profiles based on the structure of superlattice. In the case of symmetric square-shaped magnetic structures, the carriers experience collimation towards normal incidence, which is because the electrons having large incident angles would be reflected back [67]. This result is not similar to that plotted in Fig. 4.4, which shows an asymmetric transmission with respect to normal incidence. In the presence of a superlattice consisting of a symmetric square-shaped magnetic field profile, which induces a zig-zag shape gauge profile, electrons experience a zig-zag displacement of the Fermi surfaces. In this case, additional resonances are expected to occur depending on the number of periods of the superlattice [100]. This may potentially generate additional perfect transmission rings in our proposed scheme.

4.4 Summary

So far, Klein tunneling has been only investigated in two-dimensional Dirac materials such as graphene and silicene and successfully observed by direct and indirect measurements [82, 83]. Recent developments lead to the experimental realization of Weyl semimetals, which enables this kind of relativistic tunneling applications in three-dimension. Our results presented here revealed a unique transmission profile where perfect transmission rings occur due to the resonance conditions. The difference between the Fermi energy and applied electrical potential is a key factor that determines the radius of possible transmission angles that leads unit transmission probability. Also, the shape of the transmission rings is highly dependent on the barrier length. These properties allow one to control electron trajectories throughout the device, which may lead to various applications such as electron collimation [101] and Veselago lens [102, 103] for electrons in three-dimensional systems. According to the results presented, the perfect transmission regions can be chosen by modulating the magnetic fields, and highly localized transmission can be obtained in the bulk of Weyl semimetals, which may be utilized in electro-optic applications.

TUNNELING TRANSMISSION IN WEYL SEMIMETALS WITH TILTED ENERGY DISPERSION

5.1 Introduction

In the previous chapter, tunneling transmission in Weyl semimetal was investigated for a specific class of materials where the energy dispersion is non-tilted and isotropic. Therefore, the tunneling properties are very similar to which occurs in graphene but extended to three dimensions. In such isotropic systems, electrons that encounter an electrical potential barrier experience both refraction and reflection, i.e., a behavior analogous to ray optics [103, 104]. Recent developments have shown that controlling carriers in such condensed matter systems by using these processes has opened new avenues for so-called electron optics applications [102, 103, 105]. Based on this, the angular dependence of transmission probability, the super-collimation effect have been widely investigated previously in context of graphene [27, 106, 107], which showed that carriers obey the electronic analogue of Snell's law, where the refractive index is replaced by the electron energy. Thus, changing the carrier concentration in a specific region gives rise to refraction of the electron trajectories at the barrier boundary. This refraction is typically symmetric with respect to the normal incidence (i.e., identical to

Tunneling transmission in Weyl semimetals with tilted energy dispersion

light refraction in optics). Unlike graphene where the energy dispersion is conventional, in 3D Weyl semimetals, energy dispersion around each Weyl point is generally tilted and anisotropic as Weyl points are not located on high-symmetry k -points. This low symmetry gives rise to a tilted spectrum in such materials. All of the materials that host Weyl fermions identified to date have confirmed tilted energy dispersion.

In this chapter, we will focus on the question, i.e., how will the tilted band structure affect the tunneling transport properties in Weyl semimetals? Our results show that the refraction and reflection of electrons are asymmetric in Weyl semimetals with tilted energy dispersion. The asymmetric refractions can be modulated by means of an electrical potential barrier. In other words, the angular space that gives rise to unit transmission exhibits a shifted profile along the tilt direction. We note that this exotic tunneling behavior is very similar to that occurs under the influence of magnetic fields. Based on this, we provide the derivation of the equivalent magnetic barrier height as a function of the applied electrical potential and the tilt strength.

5.2 Theory

5.2.1 Tilted energy dispersion of Weyl fermions

A tilted Weyl fermion can be described by the below low energy Hamiltonian, i.e.,

$$H = V_0 + \sum_i \hbar k_i (\sigma^i v_i + w_i). \quad (5.1)$$

In the above, V_0 is electrical potential, v_i 's are velocities, and σ^i 's are Pauli matrixes, where $i = (x, y, z)$. The velocities can be different in different directions, and the sign of the velocity carries the chirality of Weyl node. w_i 's show the tilt strength, which are zero in conventional non-tilted systems.

A tilted Weyl fermion can be characterized into two groups according to the strength of tilt. The first class corresponds to the case of $w_i < v_i$, where the energy dispersion is tilted, but without any overlap between the conduction and valence bands (these two bands are just touching each other at the Weyl node). The other class, where $w_i > v_i$ causes an energy dispersion whose Fermi surface is not point-like and some part of the valence (conduction) band can be above (below) of Fermi level. In this work, we focused on the tilt strength lower than the velocity on tilt direction ($-v_i < w_i < v_i$). From Eq. (5.1), the energy spectrum of a single Weyl node under electrical potential can be found as

$$E_{\pm}(k) = \pm\hbar(\sqrt{k_x^2v_x^2 + k_y^2v_y^2 + k_z^2v_z^2} + k_xw_x + k_yw_y + k_zw_z) + V_0. \quad (5.2)$$

The three-dimensional wave vectors are given by

$$\begin{aligned} k_x &= k_F \cos \gamma \cos \phi, \\ k_y &= k_F \cos \gamma \sin \phi, \\ k_z &= k_F \sin \gamma. \end{aligned} \quad (5.3)$$

The above wavevectors forms are identical to that shown in the previous chapter; however, the k_F is distinct due to the tilted band structure. By considering symmetric velocities that equal to the Fermi velocity ($v_i = v_F$), the Fermi wave vector is given by

$$k_F = \frac{E_F - V_0}{\pm\hbar v_F + \hbar w_z \sin \gamma + \hbar \cos \gamma (w_x \cos \phi + w_y \sin \phi)}. \quad (5.4)$$

Note that in the case of $w_i = 0$, the energy dispersion and Fermi wave vector can be reduced to that of the conventional (non-tilted) Weyl fermion with the Dirac energy dispersion. The energy spectrum for both types of Weyl semimetals without potential is shown schematically in Fig. 5.1, where (a) shows a Weyl fermion type I without a tilt, (b) shows a tilted energy dispersion of Weyl fermion.

Fig. 5.1 Energy spectrum of Weyl fermion with (a) non-tilted, and (b) tilted dispersion along x -direction. The green and blue bands represent conduction and valence bands, which are touching each other at Weyl node where the Fermi level placed and shown by the gray plane.

5.2.2 Transmission across a single electrical potential barrier

The position of the Weyl nodes in k -space highly depends on the crystal structure of the host material. For instance, the Weyl nodes exhibiting a tilted characteristic are found at 0.052 eV and 0.058 eV in WTe_2 [108], which is slightly above E_F , while in Ta_3S_2 , all of the Weyl nodes are at the same energy and located at the intrinsic Fermi level without spin-orbit coupling [34]. In this section, we consider an infinite Weyl system and neglect the contribution of the Fermi arc surface states to the conduction as the major contribution belongs to the bulk states as shown in a thin film system of the Dirac semimetal Na_3Bi [109]. We note that the transmission direction must be selected carefully by considering the distribution of Weyl nodes in the Brillouin zone, to ensure wide nodal separation along that direction, which is required to avoid internode scattering. In the following chapters, we will discuss the effect of internode scattering in detail. The electrical barrier structure used in this scheme is experimentally feasible (detailed explanation can be found in Section 2.2.4).

Here, we investigate the tunneling transmission, where the energy dispersion is tilted along the y -direction. By following the same method shown in the previous chapters (i.e., also presented in Ref. [59]), we analytically calculate the angular profile

Fig. 5.2 The schematic illustration of a Weyl semimetal in the presence of an electrical barrier of width L , which gives rise to a change in carrier concentration under the gated barrier region. Therefore, a p-n-p (or n-p-n) junction can be achieved in the case where the potential barrier height V_0 is higher than the Fermi energy E_F (i.e., shown by the dotted blue line).

of tunneling probability in the case of tunneling across a single potential barrier shown in Fig. 5.2, where the electrical potential profile can be described by

$$V_x = V_0[\Theta(x) - \Theta(x - L)]. \quad (5.5)$$

Based on the Hamiltonian (Eq. 5.1), the wave function components of the system are given by

$$\psi_{\pm} \equiv \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} e^{i\vec{k}\vec{r}} \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ e^{i\phi} \sec \gamma (\eta + \sin \gamma) \end{pmatrix} \equiv \begin{pmatrix} \psi_a \\ \psi_b^{\eta} \end{pmatrix}. \quad (5.6)$$

Note that the wave functions of the tilted Weyl systems are in the same form as the non-tilted one shown in Eq. 4.2, which means that the tilt velocity does not affect the wave-function form, while the wave vector along the tilt direction is highly affected.

Tunneling transmission in Weyl semimetals with tilted energy dispersion

The above wave functions can be written for three different regions shown in Fig. 5.2. And hence, the transmission function t , i.e., the coefficient of the transmitted wave, can be calculated by using the matching of the wave functions at barrier boundaries. So that, one can analytically obtain the transmission probability $T(\gamma, \phi)$. Note that the wave vector along the transmission within the barrier region transforms as $k_x \rightarrow q_x$, where

$$q_x = \frac{\sqrt{-\hbar^2 v_F^2 (k_y^2 + k_z^2) + (-E_F + V_0 + \hbar \omega_y k_y)^2}}{\hbar v_F}. \quad (5.7)$$

The propagation angles of electrons within the barrier can be analytically found based on the conservation of transverse momentum:

$$\theta = \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{k_y}{q_x} \right), \quad (5.8)$$

$$\alpha = \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{k_z}{q_x} \cos \theta \right). \quad (5.9)$$

5.3 Results and discussions

5.3.1 Angular dependence of transmission probability

In Fig. 5.3, the angular profile of electron tunneling in three dimensions is presented. Due to the Klein tunneling between electron states in the conduction band and hole states in the valence band, the barrier shows perfect transparency for normal incidence, i.e., a behavior which also occurs in conventional non-tilted Weyl semimetals [59]. The additional perfect transmission angles (so-called magic transmission rings) emerges if the condition $q_x L = \pi, n = 0, \pm 1, \dots$ satisfies.

Fig. 5.3 Angular profile of tunneling transmission of n-p-n junction of a Weyl semimetal with (a) non-tilted and (b-d) tilted energy dispersion where the tilt strength $w_y = 0.1v_y$, and in the presence of electrical potential V_0 applied on the central region. In (e) and (f), the central region includes disorder scattering, where the other system configurations are the same with (b). (e) shows the tunneling profile in the case of weak disorder ($\xi = 1$ meV), while (f) shows the tunneling profile in the case of strong disorder effect ($\xi = 10$ meV). For all configurations, Fermi energy $E_F = 82.6$ meV, the barrier length $L = 100$ nm, and the incident angles are in radians.

Tunneling transmission in Weyl semimetals with tilted energy dispersion

As shown in Fig. 5.3 (a), the transmission profile is symmetric with respect to both $\gamma = 0$ and $\phi = 0$. This means that electrical potential barrier causes symmetric refractions and reflections at the barrier interface. This is only valid in the case of conventional non-tilted and isotropic dispersion relation, while the symmetry is broken in the case of tilted Weyl system as shown in Fig. 5.3 (b-d). Note that the shift of the perfect transmission angles is increasing with increasing potential barrier height. This anomalous tunneling shift due to the tilted spectrum is first observed in this work. This symmetry is conserved in non-tilted systems as the symmetrical contraction or expansion of the Fermi surface occurs when the energy changes.

Fig. 5.4 The Fermi surface orientation at the first and second region, where second region is under the influence of electrical potential $V_0 = 176$ meV. (a) shows a Weyl system with tilted energy dispersion by $w_y = -0.4v_F$, and (b) shows a conventional non-tilted Weyl system ($w_y = 0$), however there is an additional magnetic barrier that shifts the momentum in the second region by $\delta k_B = eA_B/\hbar \approx 6.7 \times 10^7 m^{-1}$, which corresponds to delta-magnetic field $B = 3$ T. For simplicity, we set $k_z = 0$. Fermi energy $E_F = 82.6$ meV for both configurations.

5.3.2 Asymmetric Fermi surface evolution under electrical potential

In order to understand the physics underlying the anomalous shift, one can analyze the Fermi surface orientation in the example shown in Fig. 5.4 (a), where the band structure is tilted along the y -direction, and the dashed and solid circles correspond the Fermi surfaces of Weyl fermions in the absence and presence of the potential V_0 respectively. The key factor of the tunneling transport is conservation of momentum and energy at the barrier interface. Basically, the range of wave vectors that allows electron transmission can be predicted by considering the energy-momentum conservation and hence, the overlap of transverse wave-vectors. Based on the exemplary configuration presented in the Fig. 5.4, q_x becomes imaginary in the case of $\phi > \phi_{a,b}$ and hence, total reflection occurs at the barrier interface. The allowed range of incident vectors for transmission at the first barrier interface is shown by the shaded angles in Fig. 5.4. However, this does not mean that all the incident vectors in the allowed range must lead to perfect transmission because tunneling transmission also requires matching of the spin (or pseudo-spin) alignment. In Fig. 5.4 (a), the angle range between ϕ_a and $\pi/2$ leads to zero transmission probability as q_x becomes imaginary. Such an asymmetric angle restriction is unusual and impossible to be observed in non-tilted systems. The limit angle ϕ_a can be analytically found as

$$\phi_a = \sin^{-1}\left(-\frac{v_F(V_0 - E_F)}{E_F v_F - V_0 w_y}\right). \quad (5.10)$$

In the above, we assume tilted system along y -direction, and $k_z = 0$ for simplicity. As can be deduced from the above equation, in the case where $V_0 \rightarrow E_F$, the angle ϕ_a approaches to zero, which means only normal incident can lead to unit transmission.

Tunneling transmission in Weyl semimetals with tilted energy dispersion

Moreover, the case where $w_y \rightarrow 0$ leads to $\phi_a \rightarrow \pi/2$ (assuming $V_0 = 2E_F$), which implies that the anomalous transverse shift vanishes in non-tilted systems.

The transmission is calculated by considering the contribution of a single Weyl node located at K , which can be described by $H = v_F k \cdot \sigma + w k$. However, Weyl nodes always come with pairs due to the Fermion doubling theory [110, 111]. Therefore, at least another Weyl node must appear with opposite chirality and opposite direction of tilt, which can be described by $H = -v_F k \cdot \sigma - w k$. We note that the transmission pattern is identical in the second Weyl node, but reversed with respect to $\phi = 0$. In such systems, two different valleys may experience opposite direction transverse shift at the barrier interface, which will be investigated in the following chapters.

5.3.3 Disorder effects on the tunneling profile

In the above calculations, we assumed ballistic transport without any scattering mechanisms. To measure the robustness of the transverse shift against disorders, one can take into account scattering potentials on random lattice points, which destroy the phase coherence. This can be done by using standard real space finite difference non-equilibrium Green's function (NEGF) method by using Büttiker probe connected to lattice points in the central barrier region. In our simulation, the strength of decoherence is controlled by coupling strength of lattice site to the Büttiker probe. Therefore, the disorder effect can be made related to the energy broadening (ξ), which is inverse of scattering time. Fig. 5.3 (e) and (f) shows the angular profile of the transmission with the same configuration used in 5.3 (b), but in the presence of disorder effect. Transmission profiles show that the disorder effect reduces the overall transmission and hence conductance. The perfect transmission angles are no longer sharp because of dephasing effect. However, it is worth to note that the asymmetric transmission profile (i.e., caused by the transverse shift) is still visible even in the case

where the conductance reduced by approximately 10% due to the $\xi = 1$ meV. The Fig. 5.3 (f) shows that a very strong disorder (e.g., $\xi = 10$ meV), which is enough to reduce conductance by around 70%, could be sufficient to destroy the anomalous transverse shift. Note that this regime is not considered as ballistic transport. Therefore, it is clear that the proposed effect can be observed in the presence of moderate disorder scattering.

5.3.4 Tilt-induced momentum shift and transverse Lorentz displacement

Remarkably, the presented transverse momentum shift is quite similar to that occurs in the presence of magnetic barriers. In the previous works, similar momentum shift has been investigated in systems under magnetic field or strain gauge potential [24, 40]. Therefore, we compare the system shown in Fig. 5.4 (a), with a non-tilted system under the influence of magnetic potential, where the change on the Fermi surface is shown in Fig. 5.4 (b). The magnetic gauge potential has an effect in such a manner that the Fermi surface shifts along the direction of the vector potential δk_B , and thus there would be a mismatch of $k_y \rightarrow k_y + \delta k_B$. Due to the reduced overlap between Fermi surfaces belonging to the different regions, the allowable wave vector range for transmission must reduce as shown in Fig. 5.4 (b). One can consider the magnetic step vector potential $A_B = B_0 l_B \Theta(x) \hat{y}$ to calculate the angle ϕ_b , i.e., given by

$$\phi_b = \sin^{-1}\left(-\frac{V_0 - E_F + \eta v_F \sqrt{|B_0| \hbar e}}{E_F}\right) \quad (5.11)$$

where $\eta = \text{sign}(B_0)$. Although the ϕ_a and ϕ_b are the angles, i.e., a measure of the transverse momentum shift caused by the tilted dispersion and magnetic field respectively, the case where the two angles are equal to each other gives the effective magnetic field corresponding to a particular tilt strength. For instance, in the configurations shown

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in Fig. 5.4 (a) and (b), $\phi_a \approx \phi_b \approx 0.7$. And the shift of the Fermi surface due to the applied magnetic field is $\delta k_B = eA_B/\hbar \approx 6.7 \times 10^7 m^{-1}$. This shift corresponds to the delta function magnetic field $B_0 = \frac{\hbar \delta k_B}{e} \approx 3$ T, which is the field strength required to achieve the shift of critical angles caused by $w_y = 0.1v_F$ and $V_0 = 176$ meV.

Note that Eqs. 5.10 and 5.11 are derived in the limit of $E_F < V_0 < 2E_F v_F/(v_F + w_y)$, assuming $\phi > 0$. The limit that corresponds to opposite transverse direction ($\phi < 0$) is not affected by transverse momentum shift and always equal to $-\pi/2$ for the configuration presented in Fig. 5.4.

Fig. 5.5 Angular tunneling profile for n-p-n junction of Weyl semimetal under the influence of magnetic field B_z , where the energy dispersion shows conventional non-tilted characteristic. The potential barrier height V_0 is the same with the configuration shown in Fig. 5.3 (a). For all configurations, the Fermi energy $E_F = 82.6$ meV, and the barrier length $L = 100$ nm.

The above analysis can be extended to the three-region case shown in Fig. 5.2, where the magnetic vector potential is

$$A_B = B_0 l_B [\Theta(x) - \Theta(x - L)] \hat{y}. \quad (5.12)$$

The corresponding magnetic field can be calculated by taking the curl, which leads to two asymmetric delta function magnetic fields at the barrier boundaries, i.e., described by

$$B_z = B_0 l_B [\delta(x) - \delta(x - L)] \hat{z}. \quad (5.13)$$

Such magnetic fields are well defined theoretically and already realized experimentally as stated in the previous chapters. Based on the low energy Hamiltonian in the presence of magnetic field, i.e.,

$$H = v_F \sigma \cdot (p + eA) + V_0, \quad (5.14)$$

the k_y experience a shift such that $k_y \rightarrow k_y + \delta k_B$ within the barrier. The shift of the wave vector is given by $\delta k_B = eA_B/\hbar$. Now, the equivalent transverse shift that originates from the electrical potential and tilted spectrum can be approximately calculated by taking into account the maximum and minimum points of k_y . Note that the change in k_x and k_z are negligible and symmetric with respect to $k_x = k_z = 0$. Therefore there would not be an asymmetric contribution. The strength of equivalent delta function magnetic field generated by the application of electrical potential is

$$B_z \approx \frac{V_0^2 w_y^2}{e\hbar(w_y^2 - v_F^2)}. \quad (5.15)$$

Remarkably, the angular dependence of transmission profiles in Fig. 5.5 which belong to the system described above, i.e., consists of an asymmetric magnetic field barrier, are almost the same as that of the tilted system under only electrical potential shown in Fig. 5.3. The equivalent magnetic field strengths have been calculated by using Eq. 5.15.

5.3.5 Difference and similarities between pseudo-gauge and real-gauge potentials

In general, the effect of magnetic tunneling barriers can be described by the magnetic gauge potential that shifts the Weyl cones in k -space. The electron trajectories and transmission probabilities can be predicted by analyzing the mismatch of the Weyl cones in two regions. The tilt of the Weyl fermion also shifts the Weyl cones, but this arises in a momentum and energy-dependent way [see the Fig. 5.6]. This is unlike the shift due to the magnetic gauge potential which is constant for all states regardless of energy or momentum [see the Figs. 5.6 (a) and (b)]. In the presence of a potential energy difference between two regions of Weyl semimetal, the tilt causes an asymmetric mismatch of Weyl cones at a particular energy, while for non-tilted systems, the mismatch would be symmetric as shown in Figs. 5.6 (b) and (c). This asymmetric shift restricts the allowed transmission angles in one of the transverse directions, which is similar to the effect of transverse Lorentz displacement induced by magnetic fields in the barrier region (see Fig. 5.4). Therefore, based on the allowed angular profile of transmission, one can surmise that the dispersion tilt and the magnetic field barrier give rise to a similar effect on the electron transport. A distinct difference between the proposed tilt-dependent momentum shift and transverse Lorentz displacement induced by magnetic fields is that the magnetic fields shift the whole Weyl cone; however, the coupling of the tilt and electrical potential shift the Fermi surfaces only, where the Weyl point stays at the same location in k -space. Therefore, normally incident electrons can transmit across the barrier with unit probability, which is independent of the barrier height as well as the tilt velocity. However, this is not always true in the presence of magnetic barriers. Based on this key difference between two different effects, one can analytically derive the magnetic field range that would definitely lead to a distinct

tunneling profile because of the total reflection of the normally incident electrons. For instance, the shift of the wave vector caused by the magnetic gauge potential eA_y/\hbar is larger than k_y , the transmission of normally incident electrons is no longer possible. Thus, the critical field is analytically found to be $B_c = (E_F - V_0)^2/(e\hbar v_F^2)$ by considering the relation $A_y = B_z l_B$. That means that there would be a significant difference in the transmission profile for a tilted system under an electrical potential, and that of a conventional non-tilted system in the presence of a magnetic barrier, when $B_z > B_c$. This difference in transmission reflects the fact that a sufficiently strong magnetic fields can totally suppress the tunneling transmission while the electrical barriers in tilted systems cannot lead to total suppression of the tunneling which is independent of the barrier height.

Fig. 5.6 (a) illustrates the effect of the magnetic gauge potential that shifts the momentum by δk_x on a non-tilted Weyl fermion and (b) is the electrical potential that changes the potential energy by V_0 on tilted Weyl fermion. For a non-tilted Weyl fermion, the potential energy causes symmetric changes on the Weyl cone and its Fermi surface as shown in (c).

5.3.6 Dependence of transverse momentum shift on magnetic barrier shape

Despite the fact that the delta-function magnetic field profile is sufficient to obtain the equivalent magnetic barrier strength given in Eq. 5.13, the magnetic field is typically not very sharp in practice. Therefore, it is important to consider more realistic field model to study the experimental feasibility of the proposed effect. To do that we take into account the magnetic field model given in Ref. [112], i.e., consistent with the experimental results. Based on that model, the full width at half maximum of the field profile is around 25 nm in the case of 25 nm-thick ferromagnetic layer on top of the system, and 5 nm-thick dielectric layer between the ferromagnetic layer and Weyl semimetal. In this case, the magnetic gauge potential can be assumed to have a smoothly varying profile in a particular range, as shown in Fig. 5.7 (a). Note that the magnetic gauge barrier height has been kept as the same as that in the delta-function barrier model for comparison. Hence, the equivalent magnetic field strength needed to obtain the same gauge barrier height is $B'_0 = B_0 l_B / d_x$. In this case, it is no longer convenient to solve the transmission problem analytically due to this smoothly varying gauge field. Therefore, one can apply the standard real space finite-difference NEGF formalism [30, 38] to calculate the angular profile of transmission. Fig. 5.7 (b) shows that the transmission profile is not effected too much by the spatial extent d_x where the gauge potential possesses varying profile. Finally, it can be seen that the allowed transmission angles and transverse shifts are not dependent on the spatial extent of the magnetic field, as much as the height of the gauge barrier which is the key factor we have focused on in this work.

Fig. 5.7 Angular profile of tunneling transmission, where magnetic barrier is induced by two asymmetric magnetic fields $\pm B_z(x)$ at the barrier boundaries, and thus the gauge potential $A_y(x)$ induced in the central region with length $L = 100$ nm. d_x is the length where the gauge potential is smoothly varying. The system configurations are identical to the model described in the text. However, the magnetic field profile is no longer the simplified delta function model but adopts a more realistic field profile with a finite width. This results in the gauge potential exhibiting a smooth transition at the barrier interfaces. (b) The angular dependence of the transmission probability, where all the system parameters, i.e., not specified above, are the same with Fig. 5.5 (b) in the revised manuscript. For comparison, the result with the delta-function approximation ($d_x = 0$) is also plotted.

5.4 Conclusions and summary

The findings presented in this chapter clearly show that an n-p-n (or p-n-p) junction of Weyl semimetal with tilted energy dispersion exhibits an unusual transmission profile that is almost identical to that of a non-tilted Weyl under the influence of a delta magnetic barrier. Based on the presented system, the transmission probability, as well as electron trajectories, can be analytically predicted by analyzing the mismatch of the Weyl fermions in k -space. The application of electrical potential in Dirac and Weyl semimetals generally changes the carrier concentration; however, it does not break the symmetry of the transverse momentum. Here, the results revealed that the application of potential is also able to shift transverse momentum, in addition to changing the local carrier concentration. We derived the effective gauge barrier strength corresponding to a particular tilt velocity. Our numerical calculations have verified the analytical predictions. The presented analysis reveals signature features in tunneling transport characteristics that possibly help identify materials that possess tilted Weyl dispersion. Besides, the findings may be used to design novel electro-optic applications and devices such as electron lenses and electron beam collimation.

EFFECT OF TILTED ENERGY DISPERSION ON TUNNELING CONDUCTANCE

6.1 Introduction

6.1.1 Tunneling conductance in Weyl semimetals

In this section, we focus on the tunneling conductance of the Weyl semimetals including the effect of the tilted energy dispersion. In the previous chapter, the tunneling profile has been provided for tilted Weyl systems, and results show that the electrical potential in tilted systems has similar effects with magnetic barriers as both restrict the allowed transmission angle range asymmetrically. Inspired by the similarity of these two independent effects, we design a conductance modulation method that utilizes the combination of the two effects to increase the asymmetric transverse momentum shift at the barrier interface, and thus help to resolve the conductance modulation problem in Dirac and Weyl semimetals.

6.1.2 Conductance modulation problems in Dirac and Weyl semimetals

As discussed in the previous chapters, Dirac and Weyl semimetals are able to conduct electrical current at very high mobility [31]. Due to the extremely high mobility of carriers, graphene was predicted to be a good candidate for transistor applications. However, as shown in the previous chapters, chiral nature of particles on graphene allows carriers to transmit across high potential barriers with a high transmission probability [10]. This property has paved the way for many novel tunneling applications such as the applications presented in the previous chapters; however, the absence of backscattering is not a desirable feature for transistor applications since the electrical current becomes insensitive to applied gate bias. Moreover, the alternative solutions are also restricted as there is no energy gap in such materials. More importantly, this problem is not exclusive to graphene, but also exists in Weyl semimetals as predicted in the previous chapters and presented in the recent works [59, 113].

So far, several resolutions have been proposed to overcome the conductance modulation problems. Although graphene monolayer possesses gapless band structure, a finite band gap can be induced by structuring the graphene layer into nanoribbons [114–117]. The success of band gap modulation based methods is limited because the generated band gap is very sensitive to the fabrication process, and larger band gap means lower carrier mobility in such systems. Another option is modulating the chemical structure of graphene crystal structure, which exhibits the same drawbacks [118, 119]. As shown in the previous chapters, normally incident electrons always transmit perfectly, and the majority of the electrical current is close to the normal incidence in practice. Therefore, a saw-shape barrier boundary has been proposed to block the normal incident carriers [120]; however, the complex fabrication process is

required due to the micro-scale saw-shape electrical gate. In this chapter, we propose a totally different method to resolve this problem based on a basic device configuration and without the need for an energy gap.

6.2 Theory

6.2.1 Model and Hamiltonian

The physical structure of the proposed model is very similar to that presented in the previous chapter. The only difference is that the barrier consists of both electrical and magnetic potentials, while the electrical barrier structure is exactly same as that presented in the above chapters. There is additional magnetic barrier structure where two asymmetric spike-like magnetic fields induced by ferromagnetic layer deposited on top of the Weyl semimetal separated by dielectric layer. The low energy Hamiltonian of the system is given by

$$H = V_0 + \sum_i \hbar(k_i + eA_i/\hbar)(\sigma^i v_i + w_i). \quad (6.1)$$

As one can clearly notice that the only difference between the above Hamiltonian and Eq. 5.1 is the additional gauge potential A_i , which is equal to $(0, A_y, 0)$ in the proposed model.

6.2.2 Conductance modulation based on the proposed method

The modulation of tunneling conductance depends on the transmissivity of the barrier interface. In this model, both electrical and magnetic barriers are effective factors that determine the barrier transmissivity. The conservation of energy, momentum, and matching of the spin (or pseudo-spin) alignment at the barrier interface are the key

Fig. 6.1 The schematic illustration of the single barrier system based on Weyl semimetal. (a) is the schematic representation of proposed scheme and (b) is the propagation angles of carriers outside and within the barrier region. (c) and (d) shows the effect of applied electrical potential and magnetic field profile induced by the ferromagnetic top layer respectively.

prerequisites of non-zero tunneling transmission. These factors can be analyzed based on the matching of the Fermi surfaces and chirality types of different regions.

In this section, to develop a general approach, we focus on carriers around a single Weyl node, assuming an infinite system. Unlike the previous works that focused on band gap modulation, the presented method is based on controlling the Fermi surface overlap between different regions shown in Fig. 6.1. The Fermi surface overlap can be modulated by using different external effects such as electrical, magnetic and strain gauge potential. The electrostatic potential shrinks or enlarges the size of a Fermi surface but does not cause an asymmetric momentum shift in materials with isotropic energy dispersion. However, as shown in the previous chapter and the Ref. [113], electrical potential gives rise to an asymmetric momentum shift if the Weyl cone is tilted. Here, we use this momentum shift as a first factor that causes the Fermi surface

mismatch along the transmission. The second factor is the magnetic barrier that induces a square shape magnetic potential.

The electrostatic gated potential in the central region of length L can be described by $V_x = V_0[\Theta(x) - \Theta(x - L)]$. In the proposed scheme, the energy dispersion is tilted along only y -direction, which implies that the transverse momentum shift would be along the same direction.

The magnetic barrier induces a pair of antisymmetric delta-function magnetic fields at the barrier boundaries, that cause a square gauge potential in the central region of the p-n-p junction as schematically illustrated in Fig. 6.1. The electrostatic gating and magnetic barriers can be achieved via several methods that have been specified in the previous chapters (see Sections 2.2.4 and 2.3). These two different factors that one can regard as real- and pseudo-magnetic barriers have originally distinct effects on the system, which has been investigated in detail in Section 5.3.5 and Ref [113].

The ferromagnetic layer on top of the Weyl semimetal induces two asymmetric magnetic fields that can be approximately described by

$$B_z = B_0 l_B [\delta(x) - \delta(x - L)] \hat{z}, \quad (6.2)$$

as illustrated in Fig. 6.1 (d). Assuming Landau gauge, the magnetic potential profile is given by

$$A_y = B_0 l_B [\Theta(x) - \Theta(x - L)] \hat{y}. \quad (6.3)$$

Considering the Hamiltonian (Eq. 6.1), the above gauge potential A_B shifts the wave-vector such that $k_y \rightarrow k_y + eA_y/\hbar$. There is an additional momentum shift due to the pseudo-magnetic effect due to the combination of the tilt strength w_y and the applied electrical potential V_0 . The eigenenergies of the Hamiltonian (Eq. 6.1) are the same as

Effect of tilted energy dispersion on tunneling conductance

that shown in Eq. 5.6. Assuming $v_i = v_F$, where the v_F is the constant Fermi velocity, the energy-momentum dispersion relation is

$$E_{\pm}(k) = \pm \hbar v_F (\sqrt{k_x^2 + (k_y + eA_y/\hbar)^2 + k_z^2 + k_y w_y}) + V_0. \quad (6.4)$$

The wave vectors are

$$\begin{aligned} k_x &= k_F \cos \gamma \cos \phi, \\ k_y &= k_F \cos \gamma \sin \phi + eA_y/\hbar, \\ k_z &= k_F \sin \gamma. \end{aligned} \quad (6.5)$$

And the wave vector in the transmission direction can be found as

$$q_x = - \frac{\sqrt{E_F^2 - 2E_F(V_0 + \hbar w_y(k_y + \delta)) + (V_0 + \hbar w_y(k_y + \delta))^2 - \hbar^2 v_F^2 (k_z^2 + (k_y + \delta)^2)}}{\hbar v_F} \quad (6.6)$$

where $\delta = eA_y/\hbar$. The propagation angles in the barrier region can be found by using Eqs. 5.8 and 5.9. Finally, by following the same method used in the previous chapters, transmission probability across the barrier $T(\phi, \gamma)$ can be calculated considering the wave function matching at the barrier boundaries (i.e., $x = 0$ and $x = L$).

6.2.3 Tunneling conductance in tilted Weyl systems

The ballistic conductance of the total system can be calculated by Landauer-Büttiker formalism, which is briefly described in Section 2.4.3. Thus far, for two dimensional systems, we provided conductance calculations for valley dependent conductance in graphene and spin-valley dependent conductance in silicene in Chapter 3. In these examples, the energy dispersion was isotropic and non-tilted, which means the Fermi surfaces were perfect circles. However, in tilted systems, Fermi surfaces are

elliptical; therefore, the conductance derivations must be modified accordingly. As the conductance consists of the contributions from the entire range of possible incident angles, the transverse momentum can be used as a parameter with a given value. Hence, one can sweep through the range of the transverse momentum in the first region and calculate the conductance at each given value, i.e., as schematically illustrated by the diagram (Fig. 6.2), for a two-dimensional system on the xy plane, considering the transmission along the x direction with k_y being a good quantum number.

Fig. 6.2 The solid ellipse represents a Fermi surface; and the dotted ellipse shows $E_F + dE$

In the following derivations we assume $\hbar = 1$. At each given value of k_y , the k -space area between the $E = E_F$ and $E = E_F + dE$ surface is $\frac{1}{v_x} dE dk_y$. In the Landauer-Büttiker formalism $dE = eV_B$ where the V_B is the applied bias between the source and drain. The number of states per unit real-space area per dk_y is then $\frac{1}{(2\pi)^2} \frac{1}{v_x} eV_B$. By considering the transmission at each value of k_y as $T(k_y)$ then the current at drain for each state is given by $\frac{e}{L} T(k_y) v_x^d(k_y)$, and the total current is

$$I/(eV_B) = \int dk_y \frac{eW}{(2\pi)^2} \frac{v_x^d(k_y)}{v_x^s(dk_y)} T(k_y) \quad (6.7)$$

where W is the width of the channel. The above integration is taken over the Equal Energy Contours (EECs) between the Fermi surface, and the EEC at $E_F + eV_B$ where

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v_x is positive, which corresponds to the shaded area in the panel (a) of Fig. 6.3 where the infinitesimal area element consists of horizontal strips. The panel (b) in Fig. 6.3 shows the equivalent integration over the incident angle $d\phi$ instead of transverse momentum. Note that in the limit which dE goes to zero, the shaded areas in (a) and (b) are identical. The infinitesimal area element in (b) is then given by $k_F(\phi)d\phi dE/v$.

Fig. 6.3 (a) shows the integration over dk_y where the dimensions of the infinitesimal element are dk_y and $\frac{dE}{v_x}$. (b) shows the integration over ϕ where the dimensions of the infinitesimal element are $k_F(\phi)d\phi$ and $\frac{dE}{v}$.

In three dimension, the coordinates (ϕ, γ) would then be

$$\begin{aligned} x &= k_F \cos(\gamma) \cos(\phi), \\ y &= k_F \cos(\gamma) \sin(\phi), \\ z &= k_F \sin(\gamma). \end{aligned} \tag{6.8}$$

Therefore, the three-dimensional analog of the Eq. 6.7 are given by

$$I/(eV_B) = \int \int_{FS} dk_y dk_z \frac{eA}{(2\pi)^3} \frac{v_x^d(k_y, k_z)}{v_x^s(k_y, k_z)} T(k_y) \tag{6.9}$$

where the subscript FS expresses the fact that the transverse wave vector (k_y and k_z) values are to be chosen from the points lying on the spherical Fermi surface only. The Eq. 6.9 can be re-written as follows in terms of ϕ and γ .

$$I/(eV_B) = \int \int dS_{FS} \frac{eA}{(2\pi)^3} \frac{v_x^d}{v} T(\phi, \gamma). \quad (6.10)$$

Note that the density of the states is related to $1/v$ instead of $1/v_x$ in the above equation. Finally, the infinitesimal area element per unit variation of incident angles ϕ and γ is

$$dS_{FS} = \frac{E_F^2 \cos \gamma \sqrt{v_F^2 + (w_y)^2 + 2v_F w_y \cos \gamma \sin \phi}}{\hbar^2 (v_F + w_y \cos \gamma \sin \phi)^3} d\phi d\gamma. \quad (6.11)$$

The velocity operators are defined as $\hat{v}_x = v_F \hat{\sigma}_x$, $\hat{v}_y = v_F \hat{\sigma}_y + w_y \hat{I}_\sigma$, $\hat{v}_z = v_F \hat{\sigma}_z$. Their corresponding expectation values of the velocity operators are given by

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \hat{v}_x \rangle &= v_F \cos(\gamma) \cos(\phi), \\ \langle \hat{v}_y \rangle &= v_F \cos(\gamma) \sin(\phi) + w_y, \\ \langle \hat{v}_z \rangle &= v_F \sin(\gamma), \\ v &= \sqrt{\langle \hat{v}_x \rangle^2 + \langle \hat{v}_y \rangle^2 + \langle \hat{v}_z \rangle^2}. \end{aligned} \quad (6.12)$$

We assume the system in equilibrium where the source and drain are identical. By restoring the \hbar , the total conductance of the system can be found as

$$G = G_0 \int \int d\phi d\gamma \frac{\cos^2(\gamma) \cos(\phi)}{\left(1 + \frac{w_y}{v_F} \cos(\gamma) \cos(\phi)\right)^3} T(\phi, \gamma). \quad (6.13)$$

In the above, $G_0 = \frac{e^2 E_F^2 A}{(2\pi)^3 \hbar^3 v_F^2}$ is the conductance quantum, and the integral is being dimensionless. In the derivations, we assume that all Weyl nodes have same direction tilt, and hence, each Weyl node has identical transmission profile and contribution to the conductance. In the next chapters, we will investigate the cases where the Weyl

nodes have opposite tilt and chirality, as well as the case where multiple pairs of Weyl nodes exist.

6.3 Results and discussions

6.3.1 Large conductance gap induced by tilted energy dispersion

Based on the analytical conductance equation presented in the previous section, one can analyze the conductance profile (i.e., $G(V_0)$) at zero temperature. In order to investigate the effects of tilted dispersion, magnetic field, and the combination of both on the tunneling conductance, we analyze four combinations of Weyl systems concerning the existence of the tilt strength and magnetic field. Fig. 6.4 (a) shows the $G(V_0)$ which exhibits a decreasing trend until the point $V_0 = E_F$, and increasing trend with increasing V_0 , i.e., expected behavior in Dirac and Weyl semimetals due to the conical energy dispersion. As shown in Fig. 6.4 (b), the range of V_0 where the conductance is very close to zero is more restricted because the tilted Weyl fermions have larger density of states at low energies compared to the non-tilted one. Note that we focus on the tilted but not over-tilted energy spectrum. The over-tilted case ($w_i > v_i$) corresponds to the characteristic of type-II Weyl fermions, where the density of states would be non-zero at Weyl point. Therefore, a tilted dispersion is not advantageous in terms of suppressing the conductance in the proposed system. However, this situation totally changes upon application of a magnetic barrier. The application of the magnetic barrier increases the range of V_0 over the conductance is close to zero in conventional (non-tilted) Weyl semimetal, as shown in Fig. 6.4 (c), which can be understood by the larger mismatch of the Fermi surface along the transmission as a result of aforementioned transverse wave vector shift induced by A_B .

However, the conductance is suppressed over a relatively larger range of V_0 , which restrict the conductance modulation ability of the device. Remarkably, Fig. 6.4 (d) shows that the presence of magnetic barrier on the tilted system enables not only a large conductance gap ΔG , but also a large transconductance $\partial G/\partial V_0$. This is because the total mismatch of Fermi surfaces (with zero overlap) occurs in a wider range of V_0 , because of the combination of two mechanisms shifting the transverse momentum and hence the Fermi surfaces, which are pseudo-magnetic barrier induced by the application of gate potential in a tilted Weyl semimetal, and real magnetic barrier that gives rise to transverse Lorentz displacement at the barrier boundaries. It is trivial that the application of magnetic field would suppress the tunneling conductance due to the restriction of the allowed transmission range. This suppression normally occurs for all electron energy range, which significantly reduces the degree of conductance modulation by means of gate voltage as seen in Fig. 6.4 (c). By contrast in Fig. 6.4 (d), same magnetic field profile causes a large conductance gap and large transconductance in tilted systems. This effect does not solely originate from tilted energy dispersion as only tilted dispersion does not help to generate conductance gap as can be seen by comparing Fig. 6.4 (a) and (b). However, the ΔG widens in the presence of both the tilt and applied magnetic barrier.

As shown in Fig. 6.4 (d), one can notice two critical voltage values, i.e., V_{c1} and V_{c2} , between which the conductance is close to zero. V_{c1} is the voltage value related to the point where the total mismatch starts between the incident and propagated waves at the barrier interface, which is the point where the disjointedness of Fermi surfaces occurs. V_{c2} is the voltage value, where the disjointed Fermi surfaces possess an overlap again.

Fig. 6.4 Conductance of the system shown in Fig. 6.1 as a function of gate voltage for different Weyl systems, (a) conventional non-tilted Weyl system ($w_y/v_y = 0$) in the absence of applied magnetic barrier ($B_z = 0$), (b) tilted Weyl system ($w_y/v_y = 0.7$) in the absence of applied magnetic barrier ($B_z = 0$), (c) conventional non-tilted Weyl system ($w_y/v_y = 0$) in the presence of applied magnetic barrier ($B_z = -1.5$ T), and (d) tilted Weyl system ($w_y/v_y = 0.7$) in the presence of applied magnetic barrier ($B_z = -1.5$ T). For all of the configurations, the Fermi energy $E_F = 30$ meV and length of the barrier $L = 900$ nm.

The extreme k_y values inside and outside of the barrier can be found as k_y^b and k_y^a respectively. These wavevector values can be analytically found by using the Eq. 6.4, which are given by

$$k_{y(\pm)}^a = \frac{\pm E_F}{\hbar v_F \pm \hbar w_y}, \quad (6.14)$$

$$k_{y(\pm)}^b = \frac{\pm E_F \mp V_0 - \hbar v_F \delta \mp \hbar w_y \delta}{\hbar v_F \pm \hbar w_y}. \quad (6.15)$$

Each of above expressions corresponds to two extreme k_y points in two regions in the presence and absence of electrical potential V_0 . Therefore the equality $k_{\pm}^a = k_{\mp}^b$ is related to the point where the two Fermi surfaces become disjointed, which is the starting point of the conductance gap. Therefore, the voltage value that satisfies the given equity corresponds to V_{c1} , which is given by

$$V_{c1} = \frac{2E_F \hbar w_F \pm \hbar^2 v_F^2 \delta \mp \hbar^2 w_y^2 \delta}{\hbar v_F \pm \hbar w_y}. \quad (6.16)$$

The above equation shows that there are two different V_{c1} , which are related to the direction of the transverse shift. The applied potential value that corresponds to the point where the conductance becomes non-zero again, which is the critical voltage point V_{c2} , can be found by the direct equality of the extreme points $k_{\pm}^a = k_{\pm}^b$. Explicitly, it is given by

$$V_{c2} = \mp(\hbar v_F \pm \hbar w_y)\delta. \quad (6.17)$$

Effect of tilted energy dispersion on tunneling conductance

Assuming transverse shift along $-k_y$, the conductance gap can be found as a function of the magnitudes of tilt and magnetic barrier as

$$\Delta G = -\frac{2E_F\hbar v_F}{\hbar v_F + \hbar w_y} \mp 2v_F\sqrt{\hbar e|B_0|}. \quad (6.18)$$

Fig. 6.5 shows the ΔG in terms of applied magnetic barrier strength B_0 and tilt velocity w_y , which are two external factors that modulate the conductance. We note that both factors significantly modulate the conductance gap. In the given system configurations, they must have opposite signs in order to generate a non-zero conductance gap as the pseudo-gauge potential induced by the electrical potential possesses opposite sign with reference to the direction of tilt. Negative ΔG values in 6.5 (b) reveals another point where a critical magnetic field occurs to induce a conductance gap, which is directly dependent on the extent of overlap of the Fermi surfaces, i.e., a function of Fermi energy. This means the conductance gap can be further enhanced by tuning the Fermi level close to the Weyl point.

Fig. 6.5 Effective conductance gap ΔG that derived in the text and shown in Fig. 6.4. (a) shows ΔG as a function of tilt velocity w_y where $B_z = -1.5$ T. (b) shows ΔG as a function of applied magnetic field, where $w_y = 0.9v_y$. For all of the configurations, the Fermi energy $E_F = 30$ meV and the length of the barrier $L = 900$ nm.

6.3.2 Magnetic barrier configuration

As the spike-like magnetic field profile at the barrier boundaries are unlikely to be sharp, they do not give rise to an abrupt, but a smoothly varying mismatch of the

Fig. 6.6 The magnetic barrier structure consists of two asymmetric magnetic fields $\pm B_z$ at the barrier boundaries. The gauge potential profile shows smoothly varying profile along d_x (i.e., = 50 nm). The system configurations are identical to the system shown in Fig. 6.4 (d); except the gauge potential which does not exhibit abrupt but smooth transition at the barrier boundaries. Therefore, the field strength 0.63 T induces the same gauge potential height. (b) shows the current density as a function of gate potential, where all the parameters that are not specified above are the same as Fig. 6.4 (d).

Effect of tilted energy dispersion on tunneling conductance

Fermi surfaces. Therefore, adiabatic-like evolution of Fermi surface shift close to the magnetic barrier interface does not lead to a total mismatch at any point along the transmission. However, despite the fact that the Fermi surfaces of two regions (i.e., source and central) have zero overlap, it still remains a question how smooth evolution of gauge potential would effect the transmission and conductance profiles, and more crucially, whether the conductance gap remains the same. Intuitively, the conductance gap in the proposed system would persist even in the case of the smoothly varying magnetic potential if the gauge potential height remains the same. To confirm this, we apply the standard real space finite-difference NEGF formalism [30, 38], and calculate the conductance profile for the model shown in Fig. 6.6 (a) where the parameters are the same as that used in Fig. 6.4 (d). The magnetic field profile of such a system can be analytically described by

$$B_z = \frac{\mu_0 M_s}{4} \ln\left(\frac{x^2 + b^2}{x^2 + (b + D)^2}\right). \quad (6.19)$$

The above magnetic field profile is consistent with the experimental results [112]. In the Eq. 6.19, M_s is the saturation magnetization of the top ferromagnetic layer, b and D are the thicknesses of the dielectric and ferromagnetic layer respectively. To approximately predict the region where the gauge potential is smoothly varying, we calculate the full width at half maximum of the field profile, which is ≈ 50 nm for $D = 50$ nm and $b = 10$ nm. In this case, the magnetic field required to achieve the same shift of the Fermi surface reduces to 0.63 T as the magnetic field is effective over a wider extent. The tunneling current of the system exhibits very similar profile with that shown in delta-function magnetic field model, as shown in Fig. 6.6 (b). Finally, this confirms that the conductance gap persists in the case of smoothly varying magnetic gauge potential, which can be understood by analyzing the respective Fermi surface locations in two regions on either side of an interface. And a mismatch occurs between

the Fermi surfaces regardless of whether there is an abrupt jump or a smooth evolution of the gauge potential across the barrier interface. The total mismatch precludes the conservation of transverse momentum, making the momentum along transmission q_x , imaginary, which results in total reflection for all incident angles.

6.3.3 Temperature dependence of conductance gap

Thus far, we assume zero temperature in the all calculations. However, it is important to analyze the effect of the temperature on the tunneling conductance. The conductance formula (Eq. 6.13) must be modified by adding the Fermi distribution function, such as

$$G = G_0 \int -\left(\frac{\partial f}{\partial E}\right) dE \int \int d\phi d\gamma \frac{\cos^2(\gamma) \cos(\phi)}{\left(1 + \frac{w_y}{v_F} \cos(\gamma) \cos(\phi)\right)^3} T(\phi, \gamma). \quad (6.20)$$

In the above, the Fermi distribution function is

$$f(E_F) = \frac{1}{1 + e^{(E-E_F)/k_B T}} \quad (6.21)$$

where k_B is Boltzmann constant.

Using the above equation, we analyze the temperature dependence of the conductance gap for the same set of configurations as that shown in Fig. 6.4. The results show that the conductance gap vanishes at room temperature for all configurations. The system shows less robust behavior against the rise of temperature in the case where only the pseudo-gauge potential exists [see Fig. 6.7 (c)], and the ΔG disappears even at 50 K. On the other hand, the combination of both effects, i.e., pseudo- and real gauge potentials, leads a more robust profiles against temperature rise [see Fig. 6.7 (a)]. We also calculate the on-off ratio of the proposed system corresponding to the case shown in Fig. 6.7 (a), which shows extremely high values up to ≈ 100 K, but decrease rapidly at higher temperatures as shown in Fig. 6.7 (d).

Fig. 6.7 The conductance profiles as a function of applied gate voltage at different temperatures and configurations (a) shows the tilted Weyl system ($w_y/v_y = 0.7$) in the presence of magnetic barrier $B_z = -2$ T, (b) shows conventional non-tilted Weyl system ($w_y/v_y = 0$) in the presence of magnetic barrier $B_z = -2$ T, (c) shows tilted Weyl system ($w_y/v_y = 0.7$) in the absence of magnetic barrier $B_z = 0$ T, and (d) is the temperature dependence of the on-off ratio in the case of the configuration in (a), where on-voltage is 0 meV and off-voltage is 61 meV.

6.4 Summary and conclusions

In this section, the derivation of conductance in systems with tilted energy dispersion has been presented. The analytical derivation of conductance allows us to analyze the behavior of the system under electrical and magnetic barriers. As a result, we showed that a large conductance gap can be produced by the application of magnetic and electrical potential barriers. More crucially, it is shown that the tilt velocity of a Weyl semimetal can be used to enhance the conductance modulation ability of such systems. The combined effect of real and pseudo-gauge fields in shifting the transverse momentum can be combined to achieve a large conductance gap, as well as large transconductance gradient. These two properties are prerequisite of conductance modulation and electron-optic applications. The presented results may help resolving a major problem of Dirac/Weyl semimetals, which is the difficulty of conductance

6.4 Summary and conclusions

suppression due to gapless band structure and absence of normal backscattering. We suggest that the predicted room temperature on-off ratio can be further improved by applying methods such as multiple barrier structures, or asymmetric barrier structure, which increase the mismatch Fermi surfaces along the transmission.

VALLEY POLARIZATION IN WEYL SEMIMETALS WITH TILTED ENERGY DISPERSION

7.1 Introduction

As mentioned in the previous chapters, tilted energy dispersion is a consequence of broken inversion or time-reversal symmetry [108]. The simplest Weyl semimetal phase forms a single pair of Weyl nodes related by inversion symmetry. In such a case, Weyl fermions at two nodes would be tilted along opposite directions. In the case where the Weyl nodes are connected by time-reversal symmetry, more than one pair would emerge, and the position and tilt directions strongly depend on the crystal symmetry of the material [121].

In the Chapter 5, we showed that electrons that encounter a potential barrier experience an anomalous transverse shift if the energy dispersion is tilted along one of the transverse directions. Based on this, electrons associated with different valleys would experience refractions in different directions in Weyl materials with certain symmetry such that the Weyl cones are tilted along different directions. In this Chapter, we exploit valley dependent refractions to design a robust valley filter application.

7.2 Theory

As widely studied in Chapters 1, 2, 3, in addition to real spin, carriers in crystals may carry a valley isospin degree of freedom. In recent years, valley-dependent transport becomes one of the interesting topics in condensed matter physics. Valley polarization has been investigated in various platforms both experimentally and theoretically [18, 21, 122, 123]. Several methods have been developed to achieve valley polarization based on line defects [64], time-dependent magnetic fields [122, 124–126], utilizing optical helicity [19], and substrate-induced band gap [22, 127]. Conceptually, the heart of electron filtering operations is based on selective barriers that are sensitive to the property that is required to be filtered, such as spin selective heterojunctions. Based on this, various works have been done to realize valley dependent tunneling using different barrier structures. In materials with hexagonal lattices, one possible way is the application of a uniaxial strain that induces a relative shift of the two different valleys at the corners of the unit cell of the reciprocal lattice, as used in the applications presented in Chapter 3. This means that the Fermi surface shifts in momentum space, which causes electrons belong to different valleys experience opposite direction refractions at the barrier interface between the strained and unstrained regions [40]. Considering a finite strained region, there would be zero valley polarization at the drain, although the electron trajectories of different valleys follow different paths in the strained region (i.e., transport channel). Basically, the refractions at the first interface result in valley dependent and separated trajectories, but due to the symmetry of the two trajectories about the net transmission direction, the total conductance of different valleys would be exactly the same. However, the application of magnetic field would break the transmission symmetry, which also breaks the conductance symmetry of different valleys as the valleys experience opposite direction strain gauge fields but

magnetic gauge of the same direction [22–24, 26, 27, 128]. The major drawback of this method is that the modulation of the valley polarization relies on controlling the magnetic field or strain magnitude.

7.2.1 Valley filtering based on the proposed model

The focus of this chapter is to show that valley dependent tunneling can be achieved solely by an applied electrical potential to a region of Weyl semimetal if the energy dispersion is tilted. In the proposed scheme, the valley polarization can be achieved over a wide range of parameters such as Fermi energy, applied magnetic and electrical potentials. As mentioned in the previous chapters, valley polarized transport requires two mechanisms, i.e., i) lifting the valley degeneracy, and ii) breaking the particular symmetry of transport system. Unlike previous works, here we used the combination of electrical potential and tilted energy dispersion to lift the valley degeneracy. As the valleys are separated in angular space, a magnetic barrier is used to break the angular transmission symmetry of the system, which yields valley polarized transmission. Besides, valley polarization has been commonly investigated in context of graphene or similar lattice structure as the methods that lift the valley degeneracy was already available. Here, we used a totally different method that is suitable for any material having tilted energy dispersion. Therefore, this allows us to investigate valley polarization and various valleytronic applications in a new material platform, Weyl semimetals.

We will first focus on the simplest Weyl phase where the inversion symmetry is preserved and time reversal symmetry is broken; which induces a single pair of Weyl nodes (related by the inversion symmetry). Later we will consider a more general example based in HgTe that contains multiple pairs of Weyl nodes. In this Chapter, our goal is to show how the electrons around different valleys experience different

Fig. 7.1 (a) Weyl semimetal with one-dimensional rectangular, square electrical potential and magnetic barrier induced by ferromagnetic (FM) layer deposited on the central region. The black arrow shows the magnetization direction of the FM layer. (b) shows the electron propagation angles outside and within the barrier region. (c) illustrates the valley dependent refractions at the barrier interfaces. (d) and (e) demonstrate the effect of applied electric potential on the central region and magnetic field induced by the FM layer respectively.

direction deflections at the barrier interface as schematically illustrated in the Fig. 7.1 (c) for an incident state with k_{\parallel} . This process effectively lifts the valley degeneracy within the barrier region. We then consider a magnetic barrier applied to the central barrier region to select a specific angle range allowed for transmission. We choose a magnetic barrier configuration generated by a ferromagnetic layer on the top of the central region as schematically illustrated in Fig. 7.1 (a). Note that the role of the

magnetic barrier is to break the angular transmission symmetry, and it plays no role in tuning the valley polarization. The modulation of the valley-polarized conductance can be achieved by tuning the applied gate voltage. Besides, the particular valley isospin that contributes conductance can be switched by tuning the gate voltage.

As stated in the previous chapters, the robustness of the Weyl semimetal is strongly dependent on the k -space distance between Weyl nodes, (i.e., the length of the Fermi arc). This becomes more important in systems that required valley resolved transmission. In recent works, tunable Fermi arc length has been proposed [129]; and particular materials (e.g., Ta₃S₂) that possess widely separated Weyl nodes (as large as 1.5 nm⁻¹) have been discovered [34]. Such developments allow us to assume low intervalley scattering if transmission direction is selected properly, which is discussed in the following sections.

Similar to the cases shown in Chapters 5 and 6, we consider the generic low energy Weyl Hamiltonian;

$$H = V_0 + \sum_i \hbar k_i \tau (v_i \sigma^i + w_i). \quad (7.1)$$

The above Hamiltonian is identical to Eq. 5.1, except the tilt vector $w = (0, \chi w_y, 0)$, where $\chi = \pm$ according to the valley index. Similar to the previous cases, we assume symmetric velocities equal to $v_F = 10^6 m/s$. Considering ballistic tunneling transmission along the x -direction, the incident angles are characterized by γ and ϕ , as shown in Fig. 7.1 (b). Two inequivalent valleys separated in k -space are represented by K and K' . The wave vectors outside of the barrier region are described by

$$\begin{aligned} k_x &= k_F \cos \gamma \cos \phi, \\ k_y &= k_F \cos \gamma \sin \phi, \\ k_z &= k_F \sin \gamma. \end{aligned} \quad (7.2)$$

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where the Fermi wave-vector

$$k_F = (E_F - V_0) / \hbar(v_F + \chi w_y \cos \gamma \sin \phi). \quad (7.3)$$

The electrical potential in the proposed system possesses one-dimensional rectangular profile, which can be described by $V_{(x)} = V_0[\Theta(x) - \Theta(x - L)]$, i.e., illustrated in Fig. 7.1 (d) [see Section 2.2.4 for experimental realization of electrical barriers]. The proposed system also contains a ferromagnetic layer on top of the central region, as schematically illustrated in Fig. 7.1 (e). A thin film dielectric layer can be deposited to avoid proximity effect, and hence electrons are solely affected by magnetic fringe fields. The same magnetic barrier structure can also be achieved by several different methods [see Section 2.3].

This kind of magnetic barrier structure can be effectively described by square shape magnetic barrier structure [23, 24, 59, 130] which originates from the delta magnetic fields $B_{z(x)} = B_0[\delta(x) - \delta(x - L)]$ along the z -direction. This is a simplified model which is useful to obtain an analytical result; we will discuss a more realistic magnetic barrier in the following sections. The more refined calculations actually showed that the shape of the magnetic field profile does not play a crucial role in the proposed method. Choosing the Landau gauge, the delta magnetic fields lead to a piecewise constant magnetic gauge potential $\vec{A}_B = B_0 l_B [\Theta(x) - \Theta(x - L)] \hat{y}$. The transverse wave vector experience a shift such that $k_y \rightarrow k_y + eA_B/\hbar$ within the barrier region. The same magnetic barrier structure can be achieved by various methods mentioned in Section 2.3.

In the presence of both electrical and magnetic barriers, the momentum along the transmission direction within the barrier is given by

$$q_x = \frac{\sqrt{-\hbar^2 v_F^2 ((k_y + \delta k_y)^2 + k_z^2) + (-E_F + V_0 + \hbar \chi w_y (k_y + \delta k_y))^2}}{\hbar v_F} \quad (7.4)$$

where $\delta k_y = eA_B/\hbar$. Electrons experience refractions at the barrier interface, and the propagation angles of the propagating electrons in the barrier region are given by $\theta = \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{k_y}{q_x} \right)$ and $\alpha = \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{k_z}{q_x} \cos \theta \right)$, as schematically illustrated in Fig. 7.1 (b). Solving the Hamiltonian in Eq. 7.1, the wave functions of electrons in three regions are given by

$$\psi_{\pm} \equiv \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} e^{i\vec{k}\vec{r}} \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ e^{i\phi} \sec \gamma (\eta + \sin \gamma) \end{pmatrix} \equiv \begin{pmatrix} \psi_a \\ \psi_b^{\eta} \end{pmatrix}. \quad (7.5)$$

The complete wave function consists of two spinor components ψ_a and ψ_b^{η} , where $\eta = \text{sign}(E_F - V_0)$ is the band index. Following the same method shown in the previous sections, the angular tunneling profile can be found by considering matching of the wave functions of different regions at the barrier boundaries. We calculate the $T_{(\phi,\gamma)}^K$ and $T_{(\phi,\gamma)}^{K'}$ which denote the transmission probability of electrons around K and K' respectively. We neglected the transmission between K and K' based on the analysis presented in the sections below, and assume equilibrium system, where the source and drain are at the same chemical potential, which implies that the Fermi level is level throughout. Based on the presented result in Section 5.3.3 which shows that weak disorders does not affect the angular transmission profile, the scattering mechanisms are

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neglected in our calculation in this Chapter. Considering the elliptical Fermi surface, the infinitesimal element per unit variation of the coordinates ϕ and γ is found as

$$dS_{FS} = \frac{E_F^2 \cos \gamma \sqrt{v_F^2 + (\chi w_y)^2 + 2v_F \chi w_y \cos \gamma \sin \phi}}{\hbar^2 (v_F + \chi w_y \cos \gamma \sin \phi)^3} d\phi d\gamma. \quad (7.6)$$

The total valley dependent ballistic conductance is given by Landauer-Büttiker formula (detailed derivations are given in Section 6.2.3),

$$G_{K(K')} = G_0 \int_{-\frac{\pi}{2}}^{\frac{\pi}{2}} \int_{-\frac{\pi}{2}}^{\frac{\pi}{2}} d\phi d\gamma \frac{\cos^2(\gamma) \cos(\phi)}{\left(1 + \frac{\chi w_y}{v_F} \cos(\gamma) \cos(\phi)\right)^3} T_{(\phi, \gamma)}^{K(K')}. \quad (7.7)$$

The above equation is identical to Eq. 6.13, except $\chi = \pm 1$ according to valley index.

The quantum conductance is given by

$$G_0 = \frac{e^2 E_F^2 A}{(2\pi)^3 \hbar^3 v_F^2}. \quad (7.8)$$

A is the cross-sectional area of the system. Based on the valley dependent conductance, one can define the valley polarization such that (e.g., for valley K) $P_K = (G_K - G_{K'}) / (G_K + G_{K'})$.

7.3 Results and discussions

7.3.1 Valley dependent transport of Weyl fermions

Using Eq. 7.8, the tunneling transmission can be calculated separately for electrons around different valley. To investigate the electrical tuneability of the valley polarization, we plot the conductance for varying gate voltage V_0 . We note that the system generate the highest valley polarization $P_{K(K')}$ in the conductance gap region (i.e. $40 < V_0 < 60$ meV). In this range, although the polarization is high, the conductance is very low. Therefore, we introduce an effective valley polarization factor $\beta_{K(K')} = P_{K(K')} \times G_{K(K')}$,

which allow us to evaluate the optimal conditions for high valley polarization and high conductance simultaneously. In Fig. 7.2 (b), we consider the $\beta_{K(K')}$ factor for an exemplary device parameters where $B_0 = 2$ T, $E_F = 50$ meV, $w_y/v_F = \chi 0.4$ and show that the effective valley polarization can be switched and its magnitude modulated by tuning the barrier height V_0 . As shown in Fig. 7.2 (b), the high polarization of K' can be selected by setting $V_0 \approx 110$ meV which is marked by $V_{K'}$. In the presented parameter range, high polarization occurs at $V_0 \approx -20$ meV for the K valley. To understand the reason of the inequivalent transmission profile shown at V_K and $V_{K'}$, we plot the angular dependence of transmission for each valley, i.e., $T_{\phi,\gamma}^{K(K')}$, at these particular voltage values. As shown in Figs. 7.2 (c) to (f), the applied potential V_K together with the effect of magnetic potential suppresses the transmission for both valleys. However, the electrons around K' have much more restricted angular transmission range compared to the electrons around K (see Fig. 7.2 (c) and (d)). By contrast, the applied voltage $V_{K'}$ leads to limited angular range for transmission at K , while allowing transmission over almost the whole incident angle range at K' [see Fig. 7.2 (e) and (f)]. This result shows that the origin of the obtained valley polarization is electro-optical in nature, i.e., related to the refractions and reflections at the barrier interface.

7.3.2 Fermi surface orientation

The Fermi surface orientation throughout the system is a very useful tool for analyzing transport properties of the system without applying complex calculations. Fermi surface matching indicates matching of energy, momentum and spin orientation simultaneously. Therefore, we analyze the Fermi surface orientation of the proposed system to understand the origin of the valley polarized conductance better. The Fermi surfaces of each valley in the first (source) and second (channel) regions are shown

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Fig. 7.2 Valley resolved tunneling profile of Weyl electrons around two distinct valleys K and K' . The normalized tunneling conductance of K and K' is shown in (a), where the valleys exhibit different tunneling profiles in the case of varying external electrical potential V_0 . The difference between the conductance profile of K and K' gives rise to valley-polarized conductance whose magnitude can be defined by $\beta_{K,K'}$ as shown in (b). At two chosen external potentials V_K and $V_{K'}$ [denoted by dotted lines in (b)] which yield a high effective polarization $\beta_{K,K'}$ for the K and K' valley, respectively, the angular dependence of tunneling probability for both valleys is shown in (c) to (f). The tilt velocity $w_y/v_F = \chi 0.4$, the Fermi energy $E_F = 50$ meV, barrier length $L = 900$ nm, magnetic field $B_{z(x)} = 2$ T, and the conductance is in unit of G_0 for all configurations.

by dashed and solid-lined circles respectively in Fig. 7.3. In the presence of applied electrical potential $V_0 = V_{K'} = 110$ meV, i.e., the barrier height for high $\beta_{K'}$, the Fermi surfaces are shown in Fig. 7.3 (a) and (b). As predicted in the Chapter 5, allowed transmission angles are constrained to opposite directions for different valleys. At K ,

the wave vector along transmission direction within the barrier, q_x becomes imaginary for the electrons whose incident angle is between $\pi/2$ and ϕ_a , while this forbidden angle range is between $-\phi_a$ and $-\pi/2$ for the electrons around K' . Application of magnetic barrier which is effective in only the second region, shifts the Fermi surface in that region. This crucially differs from the valley dependent shift as the magnetic barrier causes unidirectional transverse momentum shift for both valleys. Therefore, the magnetic barrier effect results in an additional shift that constricts the allowed angle range at K ; however it widens the allowed angles at K' as shown in Fig. 7.3 (c) and (d). As a result, the barrier becomes highly valley selective, that leads valley polarized conductance shown in the previous section. The allowed range shown by shaded angles in Fig. 7.3 does not imply that all the incident vectors in this range would yield perfect transmission since the tunneling probability at the interface also requires the matching of the spin (or pseudo-spin) alignment. In the configuration shown in Fig. 7.2 (c) and (d), tunneling occurs between Weyl nodes with the same chirality in the case $V_0 = V_K$, which causes the perfect matching of spin alignment; therefore the transmission profile is only determined by the conservation of momentum and energy. On the other hand, Klein tunneling (chiral tunneling) occurs in the case of $V_0 = V_{K'}$ since $V_{K'} > E_F$, causing the different pattern of transmission angles because of the different spin alignment of electron and hole states, as can be seen in Fig. 7.2 (e) and (f).

7.3.3 Dependence of polarization on tilt velocity and magnetic field

As explained in the previous section, magnetic barrier and tilted energy spectrum are the key factors that generate the valley dependent conductance. Therefore, it is important to show the dependence of the valley polarization on these two factors.

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Fig. 7.3 The dashed-lined and solid-lined circles represent the Fermi surfaces of the first and second regions shown in Fig. 7.1 (a) respectively. The conservation of transverse wave vector k_y limits the allowed transmission range in angle-space in the case of external electrical and magnetic potentials. K and K' are two inequivalent valleys which possess opposite chirality and opposite direction tilt ($w_y/v_F = \chi 0.4$) along the y -axis. (a) and (b) illustrate that the applied electrical potential ($V_0 = 110$ meV) gives rise to a valley dependent momentum shift, causing the valley dependent refraction and reflections at the barrier interface. (c) and (d) demonstrate the further effect of external delta-magnetic field ($B_{0(z)} = 2$ T) induced by FM layer on the central region, causing the contraction (at K) and extension to all possible angles in the forward direction (at K') of the allowed transmission range (denoted by the shaded angles). The Fermi energy $E_F = 50$ meV.

The valley polarization is highly dependent on the tilt strength as it generates the valley-dependent transverse shift at the barrier interface, which can be seen in Fig. 7.4 (a). Note that this transverse momentum shift does not solely originate from the tilt, but the combination of tilt and applied electrical potential. Therefore, the presence

Fig. 7.4 The effect of tilt strength and applied magnetic barrier on the polarization of K' . (a) shows the $\beta_{K'}$ for different tilt strength, where $B_{0(z)} = 2$ T, (b) shows the $\beta_{K'}$ for different strength of applied magnetic barrier, where $w_y/v_F = \chi 0.4$. The Fermi energy $E_F = 50$ meV, and barrier length $L = 900$ nm for all configurations.

of only one of these cannot lift the valley degeneracy. Once the valley degeneracy is lifted, the electrons belong to different valleys are separated in angle-space. But, due to symmetry, the contribution of each valley to the total conduction would be still same, yielding to zero valley polarized conductance. Therefore, we use the magnetic barrier to break the angular transmission symmetry, and thus, generate a valley-selective electro-magnetic effect at the barrier interface. Therefore, the valley-polarization of the conductance also depends on the magnetic field strength, as shown in Fig. 7.4 (b).

7.3.4 Realistic magnetic barrier

The magnetic barrier structure in the proposed scheme would only affect the electrons by means of fringe fields generated by the ferrimagnetic layer, and exchange proximity effect is avoided by depositing thin film dielectric layer between Weyl semimetal and ferromagnetic layer as shown in Fig. 7.1. Thus far, we used simplified barrier structure; now we will delve deeper into the physics of the magnetic barrier and focus on a more realistic field profile, which is consistent with the experimental results [112]:

$$B_z(x) = \frac{\mu_0 M_s}{4} \ln\left(\frac{x^2 + z^2}{(z + D)^2 + x^2}\right). \quad (7.9)$$

Fig. 7.5 Realistic magnetic barrier configuration. (a) shows magnetic field profile with two asymmetric peaks, induced at the edges of the FM layer shown in Fig 1. Different colors represent the field profile at different points in the z -direction. (c) shows the shift of the k_y due to the gauge potential A_x induced by the magnetic fields shown in (a). The maximum magnetic field strength $B_{max}(z)$ shown in (a) reduces with increasing distance along z , of which characteristic calculated for continuous distance in (c), while the integration of the magnetic field over x is constant as shown at the right axis in (c). Since the maximum height of the A_x does not depend on the field profile, the valley resolved conductance shows very similar profiles at varying depth of the proposed device, as shown in (d).

The above equation is the same as Eq. 6.19, except z is total distance between the ferromagnetic layer. Using above equation, the ferromagnetic layer on top of the Weyl semimetal yields two asymmetric magnetic fields at the boundaries, which are shown in Fig. 7.5 (a). The magnitude of the magnetic field at the peak reduces with increasing distance in z -direction, as shown in 7.5 (a) where the different colors correspond different values of z . However, the field profile also spreads out over a wider extent in x . Note that the $\int B_x dx$ is constant at all depth z although the peak value $B_{max}(z)$ reduces along z as shown in Fig. 7.5 (c). We note that the maximum height of the gauge potential A_x is not dependent on the $B_{max}(z)$ but the integral $\int B_x dx$. Since the valley filtering method presented is dependent primarily on the Fermi surface

overlap, the maximum height of the A_x is the key factor rather than the specific profile of A_x over different depth z . Thus, one can envisage that the variation of the magnetic field along z would not have a strong influence on the valley polarization. We present the numerical simulation of the realistic barrier structure shown in Fig. 7.5 (a) and (b), which shows the conductance profile in the case of different depths along z . The transmission of the system is calculated by applying the transfer matrix method (Ref. [30]); the system is divided into short segments where the magnetic gauge potential is spatially varying along x . The conductance of the system is calculated by using Eq. 7.8. As shown in Fig. 7.5 (d), the results reveal that the valley polarized conductance is highly robust against variation in the magnetic field along both x and z directions. To compare the previous results, the magnetization of the FM layer is set to the value that leads to the same gauge potential height as that presented in Fig. 7.2.

7.3.5 Tuning the valley polarization

The proposed valley filtering method is not restricted to some particular parameter range. From theoretical point of view, the application of electrical potential barrier in tilted band structures leads a transverse momentum shift and this shift is generally valley dependent as valleys are tilted along different directions due to the broken symmetries. Therefore, any change in electrical potential along the transmission would yield valley dependent transverse refractions. Any strength and profile of magnetic field along a particular direction would break the angular symmetry of tunneling transmission by means of Lorentz displacement. Non-zero valley polarization can be obtained at any applied arbitrary gate voltage as shown in the Fig. 7.2 (a) and (c). But, the strength of the valley polarization can be optimized by modulating the value of the gate voltage as depicted in Fig. 7.1(d), where the K and K' polarization can be optimized by setting V_0 at V_K and $V_{K'}$. The optimal voltage values highly depend on

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the tunable system parameters such as the intrinsic Fermi level. Due to the flexible parameter configuration, we believe that the generated valley polarization could be readily observed experimentally. Based on the parameters used in the demonstration shown in Fig. 7.2, approximately 100 meV change of the electrical potential is required in order to switch the polarization between the two valleys. This can be achieved in various realistic systems; for instance, electrostatic gating by means of solid electrolytes is experimentally conducted in Cd_3As_2 [44]. The electron and hole densities have been tuned to values on the order of $10^{12}cm^{-2}$, which implies that a change of Fermi level in excess 100 meV (i.e., between 143-254 meV), was realized under a gate voltage of 0 to 12 V, which deduced based on observed Shubnikov-de Haas oscillations [44]. Besides, a similar experiment confirmed that the carrier density rises up to values on the order of $10^{12}cm^{-2}$ by application of gate voltage in WTe_2 [131].

7.3.6 Effect of the finite device thickness on the valley polarization

In the first part of this Chapter, we consider the condition where the finite thickness along z is much larger than the Fermi wavelength (λ_F), which allows us to follow the continuum band dispersion without considering the quantization of k . In this part, we consider the quantization of wave vector along the thickness since the device thickness may be required to be very thin if one use gated potential barriers. Based on 50 nm device thickness we recalculate the band quantization and valley polarized conductance. In order to do that, we use the generic model (Eq. 7.10) [59, 132, 133] that describes

two Weyl nodes situated at $k_x = k_y = 0$, $k_z = \pm\Delta k_z/2$, where Δk_z is the k -space distance between the two Weyl nodes.

$$H = \varepsilon_0 + \begin{pmatrix} M(\mathbf{k}) & Ak_+ \\ Ak_- & -M(\mathbf{k}) \end{pmatrix}. \quad (7.10)$$

Fig. 7.6 (a) The energy dispersion at $k_y = 0$, where the $E_F = 35$ meV which is represented by the red dashed line. Two Weyl nodes appear at $k_z \simeq \pm 0.9 \text{ nm}^{-1}$. In our model, the application of a top gate voltage generates electrostatic barrier height (V_0) in the central region. The conductance of the system shown in (b) is calculated for $-50 \text{ meV} < V_0 < 25 \text{ meV}$, which covers the applied potential range between the purple dashed lines. These lines indicate the levels in the central region where the Fermi level coincides with, in the case of $V_0 = 25 \text{ meV}$ and $V_0 = -50 \text{ meV}$. The material parameters used in the calculations are $C_0 = 0$, $C_1 = 67.538 \text{ meV nm}^2$, $C_2 = -84.008 \text{ meV nm}^2$, $M_0 = -86.86 \text{ meV}$, $M_1 = -106.424 \text{ meV nm}^2$, $M_2 = -103.610 \text{ meV nm}^2$, $A = 245.98 \text{ meV}$.

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In the Eq. 7.10, $\varepsilon_0 = C_0 + C_1 k_z^2 + C_2(k_x^2 + k_y^2)$, $M(k) = -M_0 + M_1 k_z^2 + M_2(k_x^2 + k_y^2)$ and $k_{\pm} = k_x \pm ik_y$. The parameters, A , C_i , and M_i are material-dependent; therefore, we take the example of Na_3Bi_2 , except C_1 which is changed to make the tilt velocity comparable with the analytical result presented.

In this example, we chose the transmission direction along y , thus, the k_x and k_z are a good quantum numbers. Device possesses finite thickness d_x along the x , which yields to sub-band dependent mass because of the quantization of k_x such that $\langle k_x^2 \rangle_n \approx \frac{n\pi}{d_x}$, where $n=1,2,\dots$. The eigenspectrum can be obtained by expanding the Schrödinger equation in the basis of the $\langle x|\psi\rangle = \sqrt{2/d_x} \cos(n\pi x/d_x)$, and diagonalizing the obtained matrix (a more detailed explanations has been previously presented in Refs. [59, 132, 133]).

The quantized energy dispersion of the system with two Weyl nodes are shown in Fig. 7.6 (a). Note that the band structure is also valid in the Dirac semimetal case with degenerate spins without coupling between spins [134, 135]. This confirms that the proposed valley polarization method is also valid in Dirac semimetals with tilted energy dispersion. Fig. 7.6 (a) shows that the Weyl nodes are tilted along the z -direction. Therefore, the system is expected to show similar tunneling properties with that is analyzed analytically in the first part of this chapter. The potential energy shifts the Weyl cones and a mismatch occurs between Fermi surfaces in the source and the drain regions [see Fig. 7.3]. We consider the same barrier structure, which consists of a 900-nm barrier region sandwiched between the source and drain regions, and recalculated the conductance numerically by matching of the wave functions at the barrier interfaces. The magnetic barrier structure is also same as that described in Fig. 7.1.

As a result, Fig. 7.6 (b) shows an imbalance in the conductance of K and K' . In the range ($5 \text{ meV} < V_0 < 25 \text{ meV}$), the G_K is higher than $G_{K'}$. This voltage range

generates homogeneous junction case (p-p*-p). Contrarily, the conductance of $G_{K'}$ is higher than G_K in the remaining range. This voltage range generates heterogeneous junction (p-n-p) case. This result is consistent with the earlier results obtained based on the continuum treatment (Fig. 7.2).

7.3.7 Detection of the generated valley polarization

In the literature, valley polarization has been mostly investigated in graphene or similar hexagonal lattices. For such systems, various polarization detection methods have been proposed previously. If the origin of the valley polarization is broken inversion symmetry, valley polarized current results in inverse valley Hall effect, which can be measured as a voltage drop [20, 136, 137]. Besides, superconducting contacts may be utilized to detect valley current based on Andreev reflection if different valleys are related by time-reversal symmetry [123]. These methods can be adapted for Weyl semimetal-based systems if the inversion symmetry is broken.

Alongside of the above methods, we note that the valley current may also be detected in our scheme by adding a second barrier in series with the first (i.e., similar to that shown in Ref. [138]). To demonstrate the detection scheme, we calculate the tunneling transmission by using the matching of the wave functions in the five regions, based on the transfer matrix method. The (second) barrier structure is used for detection; therefore, it is set to a configuration that only one valley is allowed for transmission (e.g., 100 meV in Fig. 7.2 (c)). The first barrier is used to generate the valley polarization. Two different configurations are shown in the case where the valley polarizer is set to the polarization of K and K' respectively [see Fig. 7.7 (a) and (b)], which can be achieved by modulating the electrical potential to -20 meV and 100 meV, based on the conductance profiles shown in Fig. 7.2. In the demonstration shown in Fig. 7.7, the detector is set for K -polarization. It can be clearly seen that the total

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Fig. 7.7 Detection scheme for valley polarization, which is comprised of serially connected valley filters. Each one is identical to the scheme shown in Fig. 7.1 (a). The first barrier is used as polarizer, while the second barrier is used to detect generated valley polarization. (a) and (b) shows two different configurations of the first barrier, i.e., set to the polarization of K and K' respectively. (c) and (d) show the angular dependence of transmission probability of the system illustrated in (a) and (b) respectively. (e) and (f) show the transmission probability for the valley-degenerate system ($w_y = 0$) in the case of the configurations shown in (a) and (b) respectively. The Fermi energy is 50 meV, barrier length $L = 900$ nm, magnetic field $B_0 = 2$ T for all configurations.

transmission of the system reflects larger transmission when the incident current from the polarizer is also K -polarized as shown in Fig. 7.7 (c) and (d). To confirm that the difference in transmission profiles is caused by the valley polarization, one can test the same barrier structures [Fig. 7.7 (a), and (b)] in the case of zero tilt ($w_y = 0$). As a result, these two barrier configurations lead almost the same transmission profile.

7.3.8 Existence of multiple pairs of Weyl nodes

In the calculations presented above, we consider the simplest Weyl semimetal phase that contains only one pair of nodes related by inversion symmetry. This type has

been widely investigated in various material structure [131, 139–142]. However, the number of nodes, their chiralities, and tilt directions vary according to the certain symmetries dependent on the material crystal structure. Therefore, we generalize the proposed method to the systems that contain multiple pairs of Weyl nodes. There are two main cases that are possible to occur as the Weyl semimetal phase requires either broken inversion symmetry (a) or time reversal symmetry (b), which can be explained as follows [121]:

(a) If one considers a Weyl node located at K , of which energy dispersion is given by $H = \hbar(v_F k \cdot \sigma + w \cdot k)$, symmetry restrictions leads another Weyl node located at $-K$, of which energy dispersion can be described by $H = \hbar(-v_F k \cdot \sigma - w \cdot k)$. The second Weyl node possesses opposite chirality and opposite direction tilt. In the case of multiple pairs of nodes, each pair must have the similar correlation. In this case, the proposed method can serve as a dual function, so that it does not only polarize the carriers according to their respective valley index, but also according to their respective chiralities.

(b) If one considers a Weyl node located at K , which can be described by $H = \hbar(v_F k \cdot \sigma + w \cdot k)$, the other node must emerge at $-K$ which may be described by $H = \hbar(v_F k \cdot \sigma - w \cdot k)$. These nodes would be related by time-reversal symmetry. In such a case, there must be at least one more pair of nodes. In this case, to estimate the valley polarization, further information is needed, such as position, energy level, and tilt directions of each Weyl node.

To relate the proposed method to a realistic material structure, we take the example of HgTe class materials. As shown in the recent works, the HgTe class of materials hosts four pairs of Weyl nodes. The energy dispersion shows type-I or type-II characteristic according to the magnitude of the applied compressive strain [37]. We focus on the case, where the Weyl cones are slightly tilted but still in the range of type-I characteristic.

Fig. 7.8 Weyl node configuration of HgTe under compressive strain that generates four pairs of type-I Weyl fermions, where the chirality of the Weyl nodes are represented by the red and blue colors. (b) and (c) shows the reflection of the Weyl nodes on the (001) and (010) surface Brillouin zones. (d) schematically illustrates the two groups of Weyl nodes classified according to their tilt directions. Each of the green and orange groups includes four Weyl nodes. (e) shows the Fermi surface of the Weyl fermions, where the dashed-lined circle represents the Fermi surface of the same cone under electrical gate potential. The exemplary configuration in (e) indicates the upper limit of the Fermi energy where there is no overlap between Fermi surfaces of different valleys. The proposed transport mechanism is illustrated in (f), which effectively polarize, and filter the desired group of valleys [i.e., orange or green shown in (d)] by means of electrical and magnetic barriers. For simplicity, the magnetic and electrical barriers are illustrated sequentially, In the proposed model they operate simultaneously in the same barrier region.

Considering the Weyl node alignments in HgTe shown in Fig. 7.8 (a), the following points are crucial for the possible experimental realization of the proposed valley filtering approach:

i) The Fermi surfaces of opposite chirality Weyl nodes must have no overlap along the transmission direction, in order to avoid chiral tunneling that requires matching of the spin alignment as well. This indeed does not remove the valley polarization, but it can reduce the total conductance because of the mismatch of spins alignment. We note that HgTe is a proper material as there would be no overlap between opposite chirality Weyl nodes, choosing the transmission along k_x or k_y or k_z [see Fig. 7.8 (a-c)].

ii) The transmission direction must be chosen properly in such a way that the Fermi surfaces of the valleys with opposite direction tilt must have no overlap with respect to transmission direction. This would reduce the valley polarization as the method is sensitive to the tilt direction. HgTe may satisfy this condition under specific strain configuration that leads ideal Weyl semimetal case shown in Fig. 7.8, as discussed in detail in Ref. [37].

iii) Another crucial factor is the k -space distance between Weyl nodes, which may reduce the polarization due to the internode scattering. We note that the Weyl semimetal candidates proposed up to date possess large enough separation in k -space, which effectively disconnect the Fermi surfaces, and hence the transmission between the valleys with opposite direction tilt can be neglected, as analyzed in the next section.

In the Weyl node configuration shown in Fig. 7.8, one can characterize the Weyl nodes into two groups according to the direction of their tilt vector, which are represented by the green and orange cones in Fig. 7.8. (d). The electrons belonging to these two groups would experience an opposite direction deflections, as shown by the green or orange arrows in Fig. 7.8 (f). There would be an additional deflection due to the transverse Lorentz displacement, which leads to valley dependent conductance. The electric and magnetic barrier structures are illustrated sequentially in Fig. 7.8 (f). In the proposed model, they are effective in the central region simultaneously.

Valley polarization in Weyl semimetals with tilted energy dispersion

The two valley groups illustrated in Fig. 7.8 (d) and (f) may be formed in such a way that valleys in a group would possess both the same chirality and tilt direction, which leads electron polarization according to the valley index, and also chirality. The simplest Weyl semimetal case with a single pair of nodes is included in the above-mentioned case. There would be another possibility where valleys in each group only possess the same direction tilt but different chirality type, which leads electrons which are only valley polarized. Both cases are suitable for the proposed detection scheme in the previous section as it is sensitive to the tilt direction. In the HgTe example shown in Fig. 7.8 , each group (i.e., orange or green) contains both chiralities (i.e., shown by blue and red). Hence, the current would be polarized in valley index, but not the chirality.

7.3.9 k -space separation of the valleys

The clustering of Weyl points close in k -space may negatively affect the proposed valley filtering method because of the inter-valley transmission of Weyl electrons. The conservation of energy and momentum force that the transmission between different valleys requires Fermi surface (FS) overlap. Therefore, the influence of Weyl node separation on the resultant valley polarization can be analyzed by considering Fermi surface configuration of different Weyl nodes. Based on this, we focus on the limiting case of the FSs where the overlap starts to occur between the propagating states of the different Weyl nodes. Note that we assume low energy approximation in this approach. The Weyl node orientation is strongly dependent on the crystal structure of the material. Therefore, we consider the specific HgTe example where the Weyl node configuration is shown in Fig. 7.8. The eight Weyl nodes situated at $k_z = \pm k_z^*$ leads perfect overlap along the chosen transmission direction (k_z), so that the momentum and the spin alignment are perfectly matched, which is a desirable condition as explained

in previous sections. Fig. 7.8 (e) shows the Fermi surface configuration, where the solid-lined circles show the Fermi surfaces out of the barrier, while dashed-lined circles show the Fermi surfaces in the barrier region. In HgTe, the Weyl points are situated at $(\pm k_x^*, 0, \pm k_z^*)$ and $(0, \pm k_y^*, \pm k_z^*)$ where $k_x^* = k_y^* = k^*$. Based on the transmission direction along k_z , transmission between different Weyl nodes is excluded as there is no overlap of the Fermi surfaces on the k_x - k_y plane, as shown in the limiting condition [see Fig. 7.8 (e)] where the Fermi surfaces touch each other without overlap. We note that there is also a momentum shift dk caused by the magnetic barrier (i.e., not visible in Fig. 7.8 (e)), which shift the dashed-lined Fermi surfaces further. In order to derive the analytical expression that corresponds the limiting condition, we consider the specific Weyl node pair A and C [see Fig. 7.8 (e)] without loss of generality. The touching point between the Fermi surfaces of A and C can be analytically calculated as $k_\omega = (E_m - V_0)/(\hbar(v_F + w_x \cos(\omega)))$, where ω is the angle shown in Fig. 7.8 (e) which is given by $\omega = \tan^{-1}((k^*/(k^* + dk))$. The k -space distance between A and C is $\sqrt{(k^* + dk)^2 + (k^*)^2}$, and which is also equal to $2k_\omega$. Therefore, the upper limit of the Fermi energy that does not lead to an overlap between Fermi surfaces is

$$E_m = \frac{V_0}{2} + \frac{\hbar}{2}(v_F + \frac{w_x}{\xi})\sqrt{(k^* + dk)^2 + (k^*)^2}. \quad (7.11)$$

$$\xi = \sqrt{1 + \frac{(k^*)^2}{(k^* + dk)^2}}. \quad (7.12)$$

Numerically, in HgTe with particular strain configuration, $k^* = 0.073\text{nm}^{-1}$ (see Ref. [37]) which leads that $E_m \simeq 22.5$ meV in the case of the example configuration, where $V_0 = 0$ meV, $dk \simeq -0.055$ nm⁻¹, $w_y = 0.4v_F$. Note that the node separation is much larger in other Weyl semimetals. For instance, in Ta₃S₂ the separation is as large as 1.5 nm⁻¹ as shown in Ref. [34]. Thus the Fermi energy can be as large as $\simeq 496$ meV

Fig. 7.9 Effect of multiple pairs of Weyl nodes on valley polarization. The plots (c) to (h) show tunneling conductance between every possible combination of Weyl nodes shown in 7.8 (e). By considering two distinct groups of Weyl nodes according to their respective tilt directions [i.e., $K = (C, D)$ and $K' = (A, B)$], total conductance and polarization factor are shown in (a) and (b) respectively.

without leading overlap for the same configuration of dk , w_x , and V_0 . These predicted values are already higher or comparable to that we assumed in our calculations. Since the proposed scheme does not require a tight restriction on the Fermi energy, the valley

filtering system can operate over a wide energy range by optimizing other parameters such as the magnetic field strength.

The polarization and conductance must be affected in case of overlap between Fermi surfaces. Considering to the example shown in 7.8 (e). Every possible combination between Weyl nodes may contribute to the conduction. Their contribution at $E_F = 50$ meV and $E_F = 90$ meV are shown in 7.9 (c) to (h). As demonstrated in the 7.8 (d) and (f), we characterized the Weyl nodes into two groups according to their respective tilt directions such that $K = (C, D)$ and $K' = (A, B)$. As a result, the total conductance and polarization shown in 7.9 (a) and (b) are slightly affected by the internode contribution; however, their characteristics are basically similar to that shown in 7.2 (a) and (b). The almost unchanged result can be understood by the broken symmetry of internode transmission due to the tilt, electrical potential and magnetic field, which also happened in transmission between the same node (e.g., C to C).

7.4 Summary

In this Chapter, we presented one of the consequences of anomalous transverse momentum shift that is presented in Chapter 5. As a result, the valley dependent anomalous shift led to a new type of valley filtering approach, which can be compatible with all the Dirac/Weyl systems having tilted energy dispersion. The presented valley dependent conductance originates from the interplay of the applied electrical potential change and valley dependent tilted energy dispersion. In the literature, the valley polarization proposals have been mostly designed based on graphene-based structures. Our proposed method may pave the way for novel applications in electron optics and valleytronics in Weyl semimetals. One of the drawbacks of most of the previous valley polarization methods was that they do not provide dynamic tuning of the polarization as they

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depend on strained material structure, optical, or magnetic factors. Unlike previous works, our approach reveals the possibility of modulation of valley-polarization by using electrical gate bias in Weyl systems, which provides higher experimental feasibility.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

8.1 Conclusions

The recent progress in condensed matter physics has revealed various unique and unknown properties. Chiral and topologic properties have opened new avenues in condensed matter physics and nanoelectronics. In recent years, a considerable amount of effort has been spent to investigate crystal structures of materials, and the effect of crystal symmetries on electrical, optical, and mechanical properties. The discovery of graphene has led to many interesting physical consequences such as linear energy dispersion and massless Dirac fermions. As the electrical properties are highly dependent on the crystal structure, different physical structures such as strained graphene, multi-layered graphene, and graphene nanoribbons yield distinct and exotic electrical properties. One of the unique features is that the electronic states in such materials with particular lattice symmetry yield two inequivalent energy valleys, which can be treated as an additional degree of freedom similar to spin. These developments have given birth to "valleytronics". After the discovery of graphene, many similar materials have been discovered such as silicene, three-dimensional Dirac and Weyl semimetals. Such materials provide unique electronic properties that can be utilized

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in various kind of nanoelectronic applications. Therefore, in this Thesis, we aimed to investigate tunneling properties of chiral particles in various condensed matter systems and provided resolutions on major problems occurred in such systems.

In the literature, several works have focused on the valley dependent electrical transport [62, 73, 77, 78, 80, 122, 127]. However, as explained in Chapter 3 and Chapter 7 in detail, there are two main problems of the previously proposed methods, i.e., i) low conductance while the system produces high valley polarization, which is due to high reflectance of electrons; ii) poor dynamic controllability of the valley polarization, which is because the proposed methods require strained structure or magnetic fields to lift the valley degeneracy. In order to solve low conductance problem, we have proposed a filtering method that produces very high valley polarization ($\approx 100\%$) with maximum conductance, which means all of the electrons belong to the desired valley transmit across the barrier, while all of the electrons belongs to other valley reflect back [27]. Besides the proposed system consists of a simple single barrier structure, which provides high experimental feasibility. We note that the poor dynamic controllability problem is related to the factors that lift the valley degeneracy, which is highly related to the material properties. So far, valley polarization has been investigated in context of graphene or similar materials that possess similar lattice symmetries. The common way to lift the valley degeneracy in such systems is to apply localized strain, and filter the desired valley out by the application of magnetic field. Therefore, one needs to tune magnetic field or strain to modulate or switch the valley polarization. In order to solve the poor controllability problem, we have proposed a novel method based on Weyl semimetals with tilted energy dispersion. As explained in Chapter 7 in detail, effective valley polarization can be generated and tuned by means of electrical gate bias. Since the proposed system is the first kind of valley filter based on Weyl semimetals, it may

pave the way for novel valleytronic applications as well as experimental realization of valley dependent tunneling in Weyl semimetals.

Chiral tunneling of Dirac electrons in graphene has opened new avenues for novel tunneling applications, especially in valleytronics, and electron-optics. One of the consequences of Chiral tunneling (Klein tunneling) is the absence of backscattering for normally incident carriers [10]. Although this is a very interesting feature that is not seen in conventional solid state materials, it significantly reduces the conductance modulation ability, which is a major problem of graphene-based transistor applications. In Chapter 6, we focused on this problem and provided a possible resolution based on Weyl semimetals with tilted energy dispersion.

The Weyl semimetal based applications mentioned above utilizes the tilted energy dispersion, which originates from broken time-reversal or inversion symmetries. We note that the interplay of tilted energy dispersion and electrical potential change induces a momentum dependent transverse shift in Dirac/Weyl semimetals as described in the Chapter 5 and Ref. [113]. We found that the transverse momentum shift can be tuned by means of electrical barrier height. Specifically, electrons that encounter a potential barrier refract symmetrically with respect to normal as we discussed in Ref. [59]; however, in tilted systems, there is additional one directional shift of the perfect transmission angles [113]. We utilized this effect to design the applications described above, and we believe it can pave the way for many other novel applications.

8.2 Summary

The main objectives and results achieved in this Thesis are as follows:

- 1) Valley dependent tunneling properties have been investigated in context of graphene and silicene:

Conclusions and Recommendations

- We have proposed a resolution to the problem of low conductance at high polarization regime. The proposed design provides maximum conductance and maximum valley polarization, which means all of the carriers belong to the desired valley can transmit across the barrier, while the others reflect back totally [27].
- A novel two barrier design for dual spin-valley filtering has been developed, which provides very high spin-valley polarization (exceeding 95%) [26]. The achieved spin-valley polarization value is the highest one reported up to the date.
- We have developed a novel design that may resolve a major problem of valley dependent tunneling devices, i.e., poor dynamic controllability of polarization. The proposed scheme showed that polarization can be modulated and switched between two valleys by means of electrical gate bias [143].

2) Investigation of the effect of tilted energy dispersion on the tunneling properties of Dirac/Weyl semimetals:

- We have studied the Klein tunneling transport in Weyl semimetals. Three-dimensional tunneling profile has been calculated. The effect of magnetic field on the electron-optic properties of Weyl semimetals has been investigated.
- The effect of tilted energy dispersion on angular dependence of tunneling has been widely investigated. Remarkably, we showed that the electrons experience asymmetric refractions at the barrier interface in systems with tilted energy dispersion [113].
- We studied the effect of tilted energy dispersion on the tunneling conductance of Weyl semimetals. As a result, large conductance gap with large transconductance can be achieved by the aid of magnetic fields in tilted systems [144].

8.3 Recommendations for future work

8.3.1 Effect of tilted energy dispersion on the cyclotron motion

As shown in Chapters 5, the application of electrical potential in tilted systems induces an effect that is very similar to the effect of magnetic field. Under a uniform magnetic field, carriers experience vector potential that shifts the transverse wave vector. This causes a bent trajectory of carriers along the transmission, which eventually results in closed loop cyclotron orbital if the channel possesses sufficient thickness and length. Based on classical physics, the cyclotron radius can be calculated by using the equity of centrifugal force and Lorentz force. However, in condensed matter physics, a modification has to be made due to the massless property of carriers in Dirac and Weyl semimetals. We intuitively predict that the cyclotron radius can be calculated based on the shift of the Fermi surfaces. Based on this, elliptical Fermi surface caused by tilted dispersion shown in the previous chapters can result in elliptical cyclotron orbit. Moreover, the elliptical cyclotron orbit may increase the length of magnetic transverse focusing. The magnetic transverse focusing point can be valley dependent, which may pave the way for novel valley filtering methods.

8.3.2 Localized magnetic confinement

In Chapter 6, we provided a solution to a major problem in Dirac and Weyl semimetals, i.e., the absence of backscattering for normally incident electrons. This is an important problem that precludes the progress of novel applications that require conductance modulation such as transistors. Because of this problem, applications that include electron confinement such as quantum dots become more difficult to realize in Dirac and Weyl semimetals. The quantum dot applications are conventionally realized in

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semiconductor platforms as the quantum confinement can be realized conveniently in semiconductors. As the Dirac and Weyl semimetals possess various advantages over semiconductor systems, the realization of quantum dots in such systems becomes a crucial task in nanoelectronics. The recent experiment has shown quantum dot formation in Dirac semimetal Cd₃As₂, where the particles are confined by means of magnetic fields in n-p-n junction [145]. We think that the suppression of conductance (i.e., required for quantum confinement) possess different phases dependent on the relative difference in size of the Fermi surfaces in different regions of heterojunctions. Specifically, carriers can be confined by the help of magnetic field that generates cyclotron orbit, where the cyclotron radius become a local parameter depends on the electrical potential applied. We believe that further analysis on localized magnetic confinement may be useful to understand the underlying physics of such nanoelectronic systems.

8.3.3 Investigation of the effect of tilted dispersion in context of photonic systems

In this Thesis, the materials that possess Dirac and Weyl energy dispersion have been investigated in electronic systems. In recent years, several works have shown that Dirac and Weyl fermions can also be realized in photonic systems [146–150]. It is known that the electrical and photonic systems have some resemblance although the charged particles and photons have fundamentally different nature. For example, the electrical barrier structures cause electron wave refractions, which is consistent with electronic counterpart of Snell's law in optics, where the refraction index is replaced by the carrier concentration of a particular region. In this Thesis, we presented several remarkable effects that originate from the tilted energy dispersion of Weyl fermions. Therefore, the questions naturally arise; are the predicted effects such as transverse momentum shift

8.3 Recommendations for future work

and valley dependent transport, possible in photonic systems as well? We think that the tilt induced transverse momentum shift may be more useful in optical systems as controlling the light waves is a more difficult task, compared to the electronic systems. Moreover, optical systems would provide higher experimental feasibility to realize the predicted effects.

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